

EXPLORING THE ACCOUNTS OF KCAST LET PASSERS AS FIRST BATCH PRODUCT OF K-12 CURRICULUM: A MULTIPLE CASE STUDY

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Exploring the Accounts of KCAST LET Passers as First Batch Product of K-12 Curriculum: A Multiple Case Study

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Abstract

This multiple-case study aimed to explore and understand the experiences of KCAST LET passers who were first batch products of K-12 curriculum. Using purposive sampling and inclusion criteria, the participating four (4) KCAST LET passers as first batch products of K-12 curriculum were identified. All of them participated in the in-depth interviews. Results revealed the experiences of the participants: high expectations of people; difficulty to adjust in K-12 transition's content for LET preparation; and encountering changes in TOS. In response to the challenges they have encountered, they deem the following coping strategies essential: embracing the changes brought by K-12 curriculum; building collaboration with peers; strengthening communication with family; maintaining positive outlook; asking pieces of advice from other LET passers. Upon reflecting on their entire experience, they arrived at the following insights: the need to provide active participation on workshops and seminars for LET preparation; importance of fostering professional development; the need to enhance CSA for the next batch of LET takers. The results of this study were deemed significant by the participants, teachers, students, and researchers.

Keywords: *KCAST LET passers, K-12 curriculum, multiple-case approach, qualitative, cross-case analysis*

Introduction

The graduates' performance on the licensing test is used to measure if a quality education was delivered. After finishing teacher education, candidates are evaluated for preparedness for the teaching profession using the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET). However, struggles arose among the first batch product of K-12 curriculum as to the changes made when the Philippine Regulation Commission (PRC) announced the enhanced table of specifications for the subjects of the Licensure Examination for Professional Teachers. On the other hand, since the K-12 curriculum aims to offer 21st century skills and education, the changes on the previous LET examination is intended on the alignment of the new literacies and knowledge acquired by the examiners in their journey of education under the curriculum. Moreover, K-12 aimed to equip students with a broader range of competencies. It was expected that the first batch of passers would exhibit better communication, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills, making them more adaptable in the workforce than those under the old curriculum (Yaz, 2018).

In Canada, board takers of their Licensure Exam for Teachers called TESOL were challenged due to the changes brought by K-12 curriculum in terms of assessing more advanced academic knowledge and stronger educational leader. The examination for teachers were formed through higher standards than usual and more efficient evaluations. It was discovered that due to changes of the curriculum, examinees were having problems with insufficient learning materials as well as technologies that can abruptly cater the sudden changes in the level of difficulty of the examination. Furthermore, higher expectations for examinees under the K-12 curriculum became one of the factors pressuring the graduates of teacher education in the country (Barbour, 2018).

In the Philippines, in connection to the reformation in education, various first batch products LET passers were challenged to discover more and to change their ways of reviewing, different from what is usual and provided in the old curriculum. The first batch of K-12 curriculum who took the LET encountered obstacles as they tend to become starter of the new era of taking examination. Thus, the examinees were expected to become more competent and efficient in answering the Licensure Examination for Teachers (Ruiz, 2022).

Therefore, given the impact of the K-12 curriculum in the examination results of board passers, there is an urgency to conduct this research to address the positive and negative issues of this curriculum in connection to the competence of the takers in the examination. The first product K-12 LET passers is an authentic evidence whether or not the curriculum is beneficial in molding professionals that are efficient and responsive to the changes in time. Moreover, the social relevance of this study conforms to imply the benefits and drawbacks of the K-12 curriculum in producing competent LET passers in KCAST. This study aims to explore different cases of accounts which will tackle about the level of difficulty of the LET examination which will be a way for the next batches to prepare and equipped with the necessary skills and also to the institution to continue molding education students who are always ready to embrace the current needs of time.

In contrast, there are studies that have been conducted such as the studies of Abragan (2022) entitled "Research Review on K-12 Curriculum Implementation in The Philippines: A Generic Perspective"; Lobo (2022) entitled "A Qualitative Study of LET Non-Passers of the New Curriculum"; Fulgado (2022) entitled "Board Performance and Preparation Interventions Among the Teacher Education Passers in Eastern Rizal". Since these studies used qualitative and quantitative methods in gathering data, none of them dealt with an investigation particularly in multiple case study approach about the accounts of KCAST LET Passers as first batch product of K-12 curriculum. The research objective is to develop in-depth understanding on multiple cases and cross cased results to discover the effects of K-12 curriculum in KCAST LET passers from four (4) majors specifically Filipino, English, Mathematics and Elementary

Education. It is anticipated that the outcome would provide a more thorough investigation on the effects of K-12 curriculum in the competence of LET passers from KCAST.

Research Questions

This study looked on the accounts of KCAST LET passers as first batch product of K-12 curriculum. Specifically, it viewed to answer the following questions:

1. What are the unique characteristics of each case of KCAST LET passers who are products of first batch product of K-12 curriculum?
2. What are the challenges of each case of KCAST LET passers as first batch product of K-12 curriculum?
3. What are the ways of coping on the challenges for each case of KCAST LET passers who are first batch products of K-12 curriculum?
4. What are the insights of each case of KCAST LET passers as first batch products of K-12 curriculum?

Methodology

Research Design

Qualitative research is a type of research that explores and provides deeper insights into real-world problems. Instead of collecting numerical data points, qualitative research helps generate hypotheses as well as further investigate and understand phenomenon. Qualitative research gathers participants' experiences, perceptions and behavior. It answers the hows and whys and asks open-ended questions. Moreover, one of the strengths of qualitative research is its ability to explain processes and patterns of behavior that can be difficult to quantify (Brannan, 2020).

In context, this research is on the accounts of first batch product of K-12 curriculum LET passers of KCAST under the qualitative umbrella of research since the researcher seek to discover and understand their experiences. Furthermore, the qualitative research design is deemed to fit in this research because through this, the researcher collected and documented diverse perspective of KCAST LET passers under the first batch of K-12 curriculum. With this, the researcher provided a comprehensive description of their experiences to understand various cases that were studied.

Moreover, this study specifically followed the multiple case study approach of research. Multiple case study involves selecting two or more cases that share some common characteristics or features but also differ in some aspects. The main goal of multiple case study is to compare and contrast the cases and identify the similarities and differences among them as well as the patterns and themes that emerge from the cross case analysis. A multiple case study can strengthen the validity and generalizability of the findings, by demonstrating how the phenomenon of interest varies or remains consistent across different contexts, settings or situations (Hunziker, 2021).

In connection with this research, multiple case study was utilized since the primary objective of this research is to obtain a thorough investigation and understanding on the experiences of first batch product of K-12 curriculum LET passers of KCAST. The multiple case study design was appropriate for this research because it assisted the researcher in discovering the cases through direct responses of KCAST's LET passers as first batch product of K-12 curriculum. Furthermore, this design provided an insight into how the participants overcome challenges and struggles of the new curriculum in the pursuit of passing the examination.

Participants

The researcher employed purposive sampling. Purposive sampling, also known as judgmental, selective or subjective sampling, is a non-probability sampling in which researchers use their own discretion to select people from the general population to participate in surveys (Alchemer, 2021).

The participants of this study were the KCAST LET passers which are first batch product of K-12 curriculum from different majors. The researcher selected the first case through the following inclusion criteria: (a) must be under first batch K-12 curriculum; (b) graduated under the degree of Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in English; (c) LET passer from KCAST; (d) graduated with Latin Honors; male or female. Additionally, the participant from this case which is from major in English experienced shift in language learning and proficiency.

On the other hand, the second case was chosen by the following inclusion criteria: a) must be under first batch K-12 curriculum; (b) graduated under the degree of Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Filipino; (c) LET passer from KCAST; (d) graduated with Latin Honors; male or female. Hence, the participant from major in Filipino has encountered shifts from literature contents.

Furthermore, the third case was selected through the following inclusion criteria: a) must be under first batch K-12 curriculum; (b) graduated under the degree of Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Mathematics; (c) LET passer from KCAST; (d) graduated with Latin Honors; male or female. In truancy, the participant from Mathematics faced alterations in pedagogical approaches to cater the enhanced Mathematics content due to K-12 curriculum.

Lastly, the fourth case of this research was selected through the following inclusion criteria: a) must be under first batch K-12 curriculum; (b) graduated under the degree of Bachelor of Elementary Education; (c) LET passer from KCAST; (d) graduated with Latin Honors; male or female. The participant from BEED has experienced more broad array of subjects affecting overall readiness in preparing for the LET.

Each unique case represented an individual's experience and journey in taking the challenging LET within the context of their respective majors. The participants highlighted the struggles they have faced in the journey of their examination. The participant from Major in English experienced shifts in language learning and proficiency; the participant from Major Filipino has encountered shifts from literature contents; the participant from Mathematics faced alterations in pedagogical approaches to cater the enhanced Mathematics curriculum; lastly participant from BEED has experienced more broad array of subjects affecting overall readiness. As a result, these cases delved into the distinctive academic backgrounds, preparation methods and personal obstacles faced by each participant thereby contributing valuable insights into the multifaceted dynamics of K-12 curriculum adaptation and its impact on Licensure Examination for Teachers.

Instrument

Data collection is important because the explanations and findings that were made by the researcher depends on how the information was collected. Data collection provides researcher with the necessary information to study phenomena, explore relationships, test hypotheses and draw meaningful conclusions (Vaida, 2020).

In this research, the findings and explanations of each cases were given emphasis in order to form conclusions that are helpful and relevant and it also explored the relationship of each variables and discovered the effects of the phenomena or the problem, which is the focus of this study. Moreover, the finding that was collected from LET passers of KCAST which are first batch product of K-12 curriculum provided significant inferences which were also be based on the data that were collected.

An In-depth Interview (IDI) is a qualitative research technique that is used to conduct detailed interviews with a small number of participants. In in-depth interviewing, researcher invest a significant amount of time with each participant employing a conversational format. The purpose of in-depth interviewing is to get detailed information that sheds light on an individual's perspective, experiences, feelings and the derived meaning about a particular topic or issue (Rutledge, 2019).

In this study, the researcher aimed to explore and understand the participants' point of view, insights and feelings where they were given an ample time to think without the influence of others. The main goal of this research is to highlight the struggles and challenges faced by LET passers in the institution of KCAST as first batch K-12 curriculum through in-depth interview. This study focused on creating meaningful conclusions which are connected to giving substantial information regarding the main topic.

Procedure

The researcher employed the following steps in gathering the research data: first step was the identification of four (4) participants, one (1) from Major Filipino, English, Math and Elementary education through purposive sampling technique. The participants were requested to read and understand the consent and agreement form before they signed it to make sure that their participation in the research were voluntary and not forced. These forms contained conditions specifying that the informants' participation is voluntary and that they are willing to impart their knowledge needed in the success of this study.

Secondly, the participants of the study were given orientation. The orientation started with an introductory phase, in which the researcher outlined the purpose of interviews, their length and confidentiality. The researcher also made sure that the participants received benefits in exchange for their cooperation with the study. In fact, both participants and researcher benefitted from the study. The participants were given the chance to provide their perceptions based on the experiences that they have which were relevant components in making the study successful (Creswell J. , 2013).

Lastly, during interviews the data from the responses of the participants were recorded using smartphones. The recorded data were transcribed by the researcher before having it translated from raw language to Standard English language. After the translation of data, the researcher extracted the emerging themes following the principles of thematic analysis. The extracted themes were handed to the data analyst whose expertise is aligned with the concept of language research for verification and approval (Creswell J. , 2013).

Data Analysis

All the gathered data were analyzed using thematic analysis. Thematic analysis was used as a method that provided a systematic element to data analysis. It allowed the researcher to associate the analysis of the frequency of the theme with one of the whole contents. Therefore, the participants' interpretations were significant in terms of giving the most appropriate explanations for their behaviors, actions, and thoughts. As described, thematic analysis has link stages: data reduction, data display and data conclusions which were all useful in verifying and drawing the data collected (Miles, 2004).

Additionally, the process of selecting, focusing, simplifying abstracting and transforming data refers to data reduction. Data reduction often forces choices about which aspects of the assembled data should be emphasized, minimized or set aside completely for the purposes of the project at hand. The data should need to be condensed so they can be made intelligible in terms of the issues being

addressed. Moreover, data reduction often forces choices about which aspects of the accumulated data should be emphasized, reduced or set aside completely to shed lights on the topic at hand (Huberman, 1984).

Ethical Considerations

The main concern of the study is LET passers of KCAST under the first batch of K-12 curriculum. Therefore, the researcher ensured their safety and gave them full protection so that they will not lose their trust. Additionally, ethical standards in conducting were followed by the researcher and these are the following: respect for persons, beneficence, justice, consent and confidentiality (Boyatzis, 2005).

Respect for Persons is the duty of the researcher to take advantage of the research participants' vulnerabilities. Self-sufficiency was avoided to maintain trust, friendship and confidence among participants and the researcher (Rowland, 2012).

The researcher asked permission before administration of interviews and adjusted on their availability. Therefore, the researcher set the interview schedule ahead of time. This was done to ensure that the participants were not pressured by time and to avoid cancellation of important errands.

Beneficence requires a commitment to minimizing the risks of the participants rather than minimizing profits that are due to them. The anonymity of the participants will be kept in order not to put each participant at risk. Participants must be protected at all times (Brick, 2007).

The researcher made sure to protect the participants. They have the right to decide whether or not to participate in this study voluntarily. Also, the researcher ensured that the participants were aware that they may stop participating in the study if they are not comfortable without the fear of any penalty.

Consent is one of the most important way of showing respect to people during research. This process let the participants become aware of the purpose and objectives of the research study in which they will include themselves into (Creswell, 2012).

The researcher ensured that written consent was provided to the participants to get their approval. After getting their response, they actively participated in the in-depth interview. Eventually, they were also informed on the results and findings of the study.

Confidentiality the identities of the participants will be hidden using pseudonym and coding system in order to protect the confidentiality of the data as well as the participants. This means to say that all materials including the videotapes, encoded transcripts, notes and others should be destroyed after the data will be analyzed (Maree & Westhuizen, 2007).

The researcher made sure to assign pseudonym in each participant in order to hide their identity. It is the duty of the researcher in this study not to disclose any personal information of the participants.

Justice requires a reasonable allocation of the risks and benefits as the results of the study. Therefore, acknowledging the contribution of all the respondents was highlighted as they became an integral part of the success of this study (Crabtree & Bloom, 2006).

The researcher ensured that participants were given due credit for all their participation that were extended in this research. Also, as a sign of gratitude to their efforts on this study, they received practical gifts in appreciation for their work on the project.

Results and Discussion

Participants

The participants of this study were KCAST LET passers who were first batch product of K-12 curriculum. One who graduated as BSED-English, one from BSED-Filipino, one from BSED- Mathematics, and one from BEED. All of the participants have their own pseudonym which protects their privacy. Their accounts played a crucial role into the researcher's objectives to explore their accounts as a graduate from KCAST who successfully passed the Licensure Examination for Teachers as a first batch product of K-12 curriculum.

The interviews were conducted through both online as well as face to face and the participants decided on what modality they preferred to be interviewed. The researcher got where she wanted to go, and both the interviewer and the researcher were pleased with the end result, resulting with a seamless flow and open communication whenever extra or probing questions were required.

Participants had the option of refusing to any question that they deemed against their choice. The data collected during the interviews was kept in strict discretion to guarantee confidentiality and only the researcher and informants had access to any information that was expressed but was not included due to the study's nature.

To adhere to the data collection method, the researcher used her cellphone in place of the required tape recorder to record the replies of the participants. The researcher also asked all of the responders whether she may capture videos or photos during the interviews, but they politely declined and instead requested that the researcher just record the whole conversation. All of them complied with the request, with the exception of one: that their identities be kept anonymous in the research (Boyce & Neale, 2006).

Table 1. *Participants and Informants of the Study*

<i>Cases</i>	<i>Pseudonym</i>	<i>Gender</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Code</i>
Case 1: BSED-ENGLISH	Participant: Kalinguist	Male	24	IDI-01
	Informant: Noam	Male	23	IDI-02
Case 2: BSED-FILIPINO	Participant: Kawika	Female	24	IDI-03
	Informant: Rizal	Female	24	IDI-04
Case 3: BSED-MATH	Participant: Kanumbers	Female	23	IDI-05
	Informant: Descartes	Female	24	IDI-06
Case 4: BEED	Participant: Kachikading	Female	24	IDI-07
	Informant: Piaget	Female	24	IDI-08

Categorization of Data

The voice recorded discussions were transcribed, translated, and analyzed once the in-depth interviews were completed. The researcher initiated the analysis with the process of coding. Coding is a technique of arranging the resources into pieces of text segments before giving meaning to information. The coding technique was utilized to provide a description of the setting of people as well as the 33 categories of themes to be analyzed. These topics were used to help form a broad description of the phenomena under investigation.

For the data to be categorized, the themes were presented by research question and referred to as major themes. The themes that had emerged from the study were discussed and elaborated thoroughly to provide a vivid description. Then came the drawing of the conclusion and verification of point in the study in which the preliminary ideas and patterns about the findings are developed (Miles & Huberman, 1994).

The researcher took notice of the constructs of credibility, dependability, transferability, and confirmability in order to add trustworthiness to our study. In addition to the triangulation approach, member verification was done to address credibility. This was achieved by giving participants a copy of the interview transcript so they could provide comments and attest to its accuracy. So far, none of the informants have raised any objections to the transcript or provided any input to the contrary. They all signed the participant's verification form to confirm their affirmative response. The study's triangulation was made possible by the fact that it included more than two sources, specifically, readings from related literature and participants (Creswell & Miller, 2003).

The researcher supplied an audit trail that was referred to ensure dependability and confirmability. It was created to allow the research review panel to confirm results, assumptions, and conjectures. In terms of transferability, the researcher stated from the beginning that the results could not be generalized because these views were based only on the participants' own experiences in the indicated localities. Nonetheless, the researcher agreed that when the credibility, confirmability, and dependability of a qualitative case study are assured, then transferability is addressed as well (Carcary, 2009).

CASE 1- KA-LINGUIST

Kalinguist, not his real name is a first batch product of K-12 curriculum and a graduate of Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in English program from Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology. He successfully passed the LET last March 2023.

Kalinguist found it tough to cope with the challenges arising from the changes introduced by the K-12 curriculum while preparing for the LET. He acknowledged that adapting to new curricular structures can be quite difficult, especially considering the significant enhancements made to the subject areas and content of the LET due to the curriculum's influence.

He also admitted that transitioning in the curriculum can present unexpected hurdles and complexities, leading to feelings of uncertainty and frustration. Despite the initial hardships, he remained determined to overcome these obstacles and succeed in his LET preparation journey.

Research Question No. 1: What are the unique characteristics of each participant?

The data gathered regarding the unique characteristics of Kalinguist in his journey as a first batch product of K-12 curriculum who passed the LET from KCAST was compressed into three (3) emerging themes. The following themes are the: possessing pedagogical knowledge, being acquainted with the teaching profession and mastering the lesson from Grade 7 to 12.

Possessing Pedagogical Knowledge

In the first part of the question, the researcher asked him about his distinct academic background that contributed to his success in passing the LET as first batch product of K-12 curriculum. It resulted that one of his distinct academic background was possessing pedagogical knowledge. The participant stated that one of the factors why he successfully passed the exam is having pedagogical knowledge which KCAST has taught him. He also added that the foundation of education in KCAST is rooted in teaching students all of the things needed to be learned in under pedagogy. He stated that:

“The strength that I have right now is naa jud siya under sa pedagogy curriculum development and educational technology in which KCAST has taught me. Through having kanang pedagogical knowledge I approached the examination with ample readiness.

(The strength that I have right now is under the pedagogy curriculum development and educational technology in which KCAST has taught me. Through having pedagogical knowledge, I approached the examination with ample readiness.)

His informant confirmed his idea that the contents in the LET includes application which tests his pedagogical knowledge, he thought that the pedagogical knowledge of the participant was already established, he stated that:

“It is because sa LET man gud dili lang jud it is all about knowledge based but naa sad siyay questions labaw na sa Prof. Ed. nga more on application, it really test your pedagogical knowledge on how will you teach the students. I think iyahang pedagogical knowledge is really established na siya.”

(It is because in LET, it is not all about knowledge based, especially in Prof. Ed. which is more on application, it really tests your pedagogical knowledge on how you will teach the students. I think his pedagogical knowledge is really established.)

Having pedagogical knowledge is crucial in LET (Licensure Examination for Teachers) preparation because it equips aspiring educators with the necessary understanding of teaching methods, instructional strategies, and assessment techniques. Pedagogical knowledge enables teachers to design effective lesson plans, tailor instruction to meet the diverse needs of students, and create engaging learning experiences. Additionally, it helps teachers identify and address common challenges encountered in the classroom, such as managing student behavior and fostering a positive learning environment.

Being Acquainted with the Teaching Profession

Being acquainted with the teaching profession is crucial for the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) as it provides aspiring educators with a comprehensive understanding of the pedagogical principles, instructional strategies, and classroom management techniques necessary for effective teaching. Kalinguist stated that having a sufficient knowledge about teaching profession is crucial for his success as LET passer who is also a first batch product of K-12 curriculum. He uttered:

“The helpful I think first is the Teaching Profession in which we are taught about the Philosophical Foundation just like essentialism, progressivism it is like building your own character as a teacher ... of course to the LET on how will you answer the test question or how will you answer the questions that you think should be the most appropriate.”

(I think Teaching Profession was really helpful particularly the Philosophical Foundation of Education which are the essentialism, progressivism. It taught me on how to build my character as a teacher... of course it helped me to answer the test questions included in the LET or how to choose answers that I think should be the most appropriate.)

Mastering the Lesson from Grade 7 to 12

One of the unique academic backgrounds of Kalinguist is having mastery of the lessons from high school. According to him, he always finds time to look back on the subjects he had went through. Based on his statement, mastering the lesson from Grade 7 to 12 is crucial for the Licensure Examination for Teachers as it lays the foundation for his comprehensive understanding of the subjects. This mastery not only ensures proficiency in the core subjects, but also cultivates his knowledge needed for his success in the LET. Kalinguist stated that:

“They will always say nga kabalo ba mo nga ang Gen Ed. sa LET makita lang sa High School especially sa old curriculum? and karon makita pud siya sa Senior High School nga curriculum so that is why I always look back on the subjects. I really think it is really helpful for me to know our subjects starting from Grade 7 to Grade 12.”

(They will always say, do you know that Gen Ed in LET can just be found in High School especially in old curriculum? and now it is also added in Senior High School, so that is why I always look back on the subjects. I really think it is really helpful for me to know our subjects starting from Grade 7 to Grade 12.)

Noam (pseudonym), his informant affirmed his responses as he added that the topic that were most beneficial for Kalinguist in LET preparation is his general knowledge learned from Grade 7 to Grade 12.

“I think the topic that were most beneficial for him in preparing for the LET is all the topics jud...like overall topics learned from Grade 7 to 12 which is nigawas sa exam.”

(I think the topics that were most beneficial for him in preparing for the LET is all the topics like overall topics learned from Grade 7 to 12 which was really covered in the exam.)

Research Question No. 2: What are the challenges of each case of KCAST LET passers as first batch product of K-12 curriculum?

In the second question, the participant was asked about the challenges he has experienced as a KCAST LET passer who are first batch product of K-12 curriculum His responses undergo thematic analysis and the researcher identified three emerging themes. The emerging themes that were formed are: high expectation of people, difficulty on adjusting to other people’s study routine and challenge in finding friends in the review center.

High Expectation of People

High expectations from society pose a challenge for Kalinguist as KCAST LET passer who is first batch of K-12 curriculum because he faced pressure to meet the standards set by his family, community, and peers. He disclosed that expectations created feelings of stress and anxiety, making it harder for him to perform his best during the exam.

“Pag-abot na sa ano, examination namo nga part, month na sa examination namo, nag chat mana amoang kuan gud, review master ana siya na “ready na ba mo mag top?” didto murag wala nako kasabot sa akoang gibati, hala nag expect man diay na sila ug ingon ana ang mahitabo sa akoa diay.”

(During the month of examination, our review master messaged me saying “are you ready to top the board” and when I read that I do not know what to feel anymore, they expected that I will top the board.)

His friend Noam also confirmed that a lot of people really expected for Kalinguist to perform well in the exam given the fact that people thought that as a first batch product of K-12, he was capable enough to pass the examination. Additionally, his Latin honors added more pressure as people tend to think that he was not having a hard time reviewing for the examination.

“as he graduated with Latin honors he likely faced social challenges like people expected him to be very good to the point nga ang uban tao nagahuna huna nga wala siya galisod,.. “

(as he graduated with Latin honors he likely faced social challenges like people expected him to be very good to the point that some people think that he is not having a hard time...)

Difficulty on Adjusting to Other People’s Study Routine

Adjusting to other people's study routines in the review center is a challenge for Kalinguist. This difficulty arose because his classmates in the review center has their own unique way of learning and studying. Kalinguist preferred studying in the morning, while his classmates preferred late at night. He honestly stated that he was pressured to conform to the study habits of others, even if it doesn't suit him personally.

“Mag study mi mga 10 mi, ang study time is from 1:00 a.m. to 5:00 am. tapos ang amoang review ana is that 7:30 to 12 noon, unya mag ano ko ba, magduha duha kog apil sa ila kay murag mamatay naman siguro ko ana.”

(We are 10 in the group and our study time is from 1:00 A.M. to 5:00 A.M. then our review is from 7:30 A.M. to 12:00 noon, then I am having doubt if I will join them because I think I might die.)

Challenge in Finding Friends in the Review Center

Kalinguist struggled to find friends in the review center. This challenge arose for him since none of his classmates from college are with him during the review period. He found it hard to look for someone who was easy to get close with because his classmates in the review center have different educational backgrounds. He stated in the interview that adjusting to new study habits and coping with the pressure of the LET made it harder to connect with others.

“Lisod jud mangita ug friend nga dali maka close nimo kay it is just 6 to 7 months nga review so basically you are just focusing on how to pass the examination pero for me in my case, like although naa lang ko sa kilid kilid, maglisod jud ko or dili jud ko ganahan makipagstorya sa laing tao pero yun nga mapugos ko kay wala man koy makuha sa akong sarili if I just have to sit there relaxed or I have to sleep my problem.”

(It is hard to find a friend that you can easily be closed with for the reason that it is just 6 to 7 months of review so basically you are just focusing on how to pass the examination but for me, in my case, like although I am just in the side, I do not want to talk with people but I do not have choice because I will not get anything if I just have to sit there relaxed or I have to sleep my problem.)

His friend, Noam, agreed with this idea that he was really challenged in connecting with other people in the review center and sometimes he felt isolated since he was a far from his friends from college.

“na story niya sa akoa sad nga wala sad kaayo siyay friends didtoa sa review center maong usahay maka feel siya nga he is alone...”

(He told me that he does not have many friends at the review center, so sometimes he feels like he is alone...)

Research Question No. 3: What are the ways of coping on the challenges of each case of KCAST LET passers as first batch product of K-12 curriculum?

In the third question, the participant was asked on how he cope with the challenges he has experienced. This includes the strategy, techniques, and steps they employ in facing challenges they encountered. In the response of the participant, the researcher identified four themes in the coding process, which are: Embracing the Changes brought by K-12 Curriculum, Building Collaboration with Peers, Strengthening Communication with Family, Asking Pieces of Advice to other LET Passers.

Embracing the Changes brought by K-12 Curriculum

One of the coping mechanisms that Kalinguist used to surpass all the challenges as first batch product of K-12 curriculum in his journey in passing the LET was to accept his fate and to be open for innovation. While K-12 curriculum brought challenges, Kalinguist embraced the curriculum and strived to follow its philosophies, vision and mission.

“What all of us did is we have to embrace the new curriculum especially that we are being introduced with the K-12 itself we do not know what future offers us so therefore, kung unsa man na ang philosophies, vision and mission sa atoang school if that changes all of the things will follow so we have to embrace this.” (IDI-01)

(What all of us did is we have to embrace the new curriculum especially that we are being introduced with the K-12 itself we do not know what future offers us so therefore, if ever the philosophies, vision and mission of our school changes, all of the things will follow so we have to embrace this.)

To support Kalinguist’s idea, his informant agreed by stating that he easily adapted to the changes in the curriculum by knowing how to embrace it.

“I think he easily adapt to changes by embracing the curriculum lang gyud...” (IDI-02)

(I think he easily adapts to changes by embracing the curriculum.)

Building Collaboration with Peers

Another strategy that the participant used in coping to the challenges was to build collaboration with his peers. He stated that in his classroom before, they fostered love, support and understanding that became their strategy in understanding the diversity of every one and creating something that was beneficial for them.

“Within the school, inside the classroom, what we foster is love, support and understanding. So that made me or that became a strategy for me that I should also bring in college like I have to understand that all of the people are different, I have to understand that we have come on terms that we have different ideas but we should stick on something that is beneficial for us.” (IDI-01)

Similarly, Noam, his informant, confirmed Kalinguist’s idea as he stated that before, they were really studying together with their friends to discuss topics that were hard and to share resources in which they can all benefit from. He uttered:

“makita sad nako before and kauban mi nga naga study with classmates to share notes and discuss difficult subjects.”

(I can see it before and we study together with classmates to share notes and discuss difficult subjects.)

Strengthening Communication with Family

For Kalinguist, strengthening communication with his family was also a coping strategy for him to surpass all the challenges as a first batch product of K-12 curriculum in his journey in passing the LET. For him, it was a helpful way to cope with the challenges of studying for and passing the LET (Licensure Examination for Teachers) because his family provided him with emotional support and encouragement. He uttered that his family helped him manage stress by offering advice or assistance when needed.

“Talk with my family especially if I cannot contain it anymore, I have a lot of things in mind especially that I am close to being professional, my last step to get a license, you have to talk with someone especially your loved ones. Talk with them or say what your problems.”

Asking Pieces of Advice from other LET Passers

Asking for advice from other LET passers who took the old curriculum was one of the helpful ways that Kalinguist used in coping with the challenges of passing the LET exam under the new K-12 curriculum. These experienced individuals have gone through similar experiences and offered valuable insights and tips based on their own success. As Kalinguist listened to their advice, he have gained useful strategies and confidence, which boosted his motivation during that time. He stated that:

“For me kay ang akoang ginakuhaan ug advice is kadtong mga topnotcher gud nga mga English majors sa una although wala ko kaila sa ilaha. I messaged them on Facebook, ask their opinions on unsaon nila pag study unsa ilahang mga study habits, unsa ilahang makaingon sa amoa, sa mga newbatch.”

(For me I get advices from the top notchers before who are English Majors, even if I do not know them personally, I messaged them on Facebook, ask their opinions on how they study? What are their study habits? What they can say for us who are new batch.)

Research Question No. 4: What are the insights of each case of KCAST LET passers as first batch product of K-12 curriculum?

The remarkable effectiveness of insights may be shown in the fact that even one piece of guidance can assist to overcome obstacles. In the last set of questions, the participant was asked to provide his thoughts on his experiences and the challenges he had as a first batch product of K-12 curriculum in his journey in passing the LET. From his answers, the researcher identified the following main themes:

the need to be resilient in facing challenges, importance of parental support during the journey, the need to understand the format of the Licensure Exam and importance of fostering professional development.

The Need to be Resilient in Facing Challenges

According to Kalinguist, even when posed with difficulties in dealing with the changes in the curriculum, one must keep in mind that although the process is tiring, at the end of the day you will realized that it is important to have resiliency especially that it is one of the common trait of Filipinos. He uttered that:

“You have to be resilient with the new experience you have especially if it’s difficult it’s okay to complain at first that the process is tiresome but of course as a Filipino, you have resiliency.”

In addition to what Kalinguist stated, Noam also confirmed his idea that during his LET preparation journey, he encountered problems as first batch product of K-12 but he always knew how to handle those problems and he keep in mind the importance of resiliency in his journey in passing the Licensure Examination for Teacher (LET).

“siguro nakabalo siya kung unsa ka importante nga naa kay resilience gani kay wala kay mahimo ug magpadala raka sa mga struggles.” (maybe he knows how important it is to have resilience because you cannot gain anything if you will give in to struggles.)

Importance of Parental Support During the Journey

During the interview, Kalinguist highlighted that his parents provided encouragement, understanding, and resources that made a big difference in his preparation journey. He recommended to always have time with family because through parental support, aspiring LET passer can feel more confident and motivated to achieve their goal of passing the exam and pursuing their dreams.

“Dapat your parents are your number one supporters and dapat kay mag support sila sa imoha always, so that is why your parents ask them and try to like always ano have time with your family kay very busy na pud ang life specially if mag review ka...”

(Your parents should be your number one supporters and they should support you always, so that is why ask your parents and try to like always have time with your family it’s because life is very busy especially if you’re reviewing...)

The Need to Understand the Format of the Licensure Exam

Another insight Kalinguist shared from his experience as KCAST LET passer who is also a first batch product of K-12 curriculum is the need to understand the format of the Licensure Exam, he stated that for the next batches of LET takers they need to understand the LET format by comprehending the questions well. He suggested that:

“They have to understand the LET format, for example is that ang question itself are experience usually mga experiences and of course if wala pajud kay idea kung unsa nga mga question ang mugawas, you have to buy books although lahi ang questions but you can change no nga parehas sila ug information like parehas sila ug way sa pag answer...”

(They have to understand the LET format, for example the questions itself are experience, usually, experiences and of course if you do not have idea on the possible questions, you have to buy books although the question is different but you change it until the information would give clues into the right way to answer.)

Importance of Fostering Professional Development

In the data gathered from the responses of Kalinguist, he suggested that the institution should need to provide importance in fostering professional development. From his viewpoint, he said that is important for the institution of KCAST to foster professional development because it helps students to enhance their skills and knowledge further. Even though they have completed their formal education, ongoing learning is crucial to stay updated with current teaching methods, educational trends, and content changes in the LET exam. Through professional development, they can gain new insights, strategies, and resources to better prepare for the exam, increasing their chances of success. He suggested that:

“Hopefully mas ma strengthen pa nila ang professional development sa mga students karon especially mga 4th years and 3rd year students kay naa may Teaching Profession karon nga subject ang mga 3rd year hopefully ang teacher ana ninyo is that they would be kanang critical, they would be more kanang knowledgeable about giving you the code of ethics and the philosophy of education...”

(Hopefully they can strengthen more the professional development to the students now sa mga students karon especially to the 4th year and 3rd year students especially that the 3rd year has the Teaching Profession subject. Hopefully that your teacher would be critical and they would be more knowledgeable about giving you the code of ethics and the philosophy of education...)

CASE 2- KA-WIKA

Kawika, not her real name is a first batch product of K-12 curriculum and a graduate of Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Filipino program from Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology. She successfully passed the LET last March 2023.

Kawika acknowledged that she had a hard time in embracing the changes made by the K-12 transition especially that the pressure to be on top is always within her. She admitted that as a first batch product of K-12, she was expected to be competent and excellent in all ways and that created a drive within her to create methods or techniques to approach the changes that was associated with the new curriculum.

Research Question No. 1: What are the unique characteristics of each case of KCAST LET passers who are first batch products of K-12 curriculum?

In the first main question, which is about the unique characteristics of the participant, there are three emerging themes that the researcher has found after coding the responses. These themes are: experiencing OJT; readiness in answering Professional Education or Prof. Ed. and nurturing comprehensive educational foundation.

Experiencing OJT

In the moment the researcher asked Kawika about what is her distinct academic background which she thought the most beneficial in her success as KCAST LET passer who are a first batch product of K-12 curriculum, she stated that experiencing OJT helped her to be acquainted with the practical application of knowledge which is needed during the Licensure Examination. She uttered that:

“The distinct academic background that helped me in my academic journey, specifically the on the job training or the OJT. Which is nag focus jud siya sa akong major during my OJT as Filipino major. So as Filipino Major atong nag OJT ko, I was tasked to do many practical works like maghimo ug Masusing Banghay Aralin for every topic or magpa- present sa mga students ug engaging nga activities and those things are very relevant sa LET examination.”

(The distinct academic background that helped me in my academic journey, is on the job training or the OJT. In which it focuses in my major during my OJT as Filipino Major. So as Filipino Major when I was in OJT, I was tasked to do many practical works like making Masusing Banghay Aralin (Lesson Plan) for every topic or letting the students present engaging activities and those things are very relevant in LET examination.)

Readiness in Answering Professional Education or Prof. Ed.

During the interview of the researcher to Kawika, she stated that as a first batch product of K-12 curriculum, the advancement of topics and knowledge enabled her to grasp easily the questions included in the licensure examination. Additionally, she admitted that the curriculum contributed to her competence in the professional education which also holds a big percentage for the overall examination’s results. She professed that her readiness in answering Prof. Ed. was one of her strengths and distinct qualities

“Grabe ang advancement sa topics and knowledge nga na contribute sa K-12 curriculum sa akoa and even in terms sa Prof. Ed which is we all know nga isa jud pud na siya sa dako jud ug percentage sa LET, wala kayo ko naglisod pag-abot sa Prof. Ed it is because na-cover na siya sa Senior High and College nako and that’s one of the reason nga para sa ako dali lang ang Prof. Ed.”

(The advancement of topics and knowledge that contributed to my K-12 curriculum is great and even in terms of Prof. Ed which is we all know that it is also one of the big percentage in LET, I did not have any difficulty as for Prof. Ed, it's because it was covered by my Senior High and College and that's one of the reasons that Prof. Ed is easy for me.)

Nurturing Comprehensive Educational Foundation

The K-12 curriculum typically emphasizes holistic development, encompassing cognitive, emotional, social, and physical aspects. This holistic approach fosters well-rounded individuals who are better equipped to tackle challenges, including those encountered in professional exams like the LET. Kawika shared that one of her unique characteristics as a LET passer from KCAST who is also a product of first batch K-12 curriculum is how her comprehensive educational foundation was nurtured and how she gained understanding on the subject areas and the test structure of the exam.

“K-12 program helps me understand the subject areas and the test structure of the exam or LET through sa pag provide sa akoa ug detailed and comprehensive nga educational foundation like ang general and professional education is also in my major. I think it is because ang K-12 curriculum objectives and goals kay align jud siya sa LET content nga gi-take nako nga exam and mao sad siguro ang nakatabang sa ako nganong naka-answer pud ko saa mga question.”

(K-12 program helps me understand the subject areas and the test structure of the exam or LET through providing me with a detailed and comprehensive educational foundation like general and professional education is also in my major. I think it is because the K-12 curriculum objectives and goals are aligned with the LET content that I took as an exam and that was probably what helped me why I was able to answer the questions.)

Research Question No. 2: What are the challenges of each case of KCAST LET passers as first batch product of K-12 curriculum?

During the interview, Kawika had the opportunity to share her personal challenges as a KCAST LET passer who is also a product of K-12 curriculum. Through thematic analysis, the researcher identified five emerging themes. These themes are: high expectation of

people, hardships in managing overload of contents, difficulty to adjust in K-12 transition's contents for LET Preparation, encountering changes in TOS

High Expectation of People

When Kawika was asked by the researcher about the challenges she has faced during the journey of taking the licensure exam as a first batch product of K-12 curriculum, Kawika expressed that she was afraid not to meet the expectations of other people for her. Additionally, the pressure that she also felt was her uncertainty about whether her classmates would pass and she would not.

“Ang thought ba nga hala first batch mi unya what if di ko kapasar? Unya daghan na kaayo ug expectation ang mga tao unya ang uban makapasar unya ako dili makapasar”

(The thought that we are the first batch and then what if I do not pass? Then people have a lot of expectations and what if others will pass and then I will not.)

In truancy, Kawika's informant named Rizal (pseudonym) confirmed that she really faced the hurdles brought by the expectations of other people given the fact that she was a product of the first batch K-12 curriculum and the people around her have big expectation as they look forward to see the outcome of the changed curriculum, Rizal said that due to this expectation, Kawika felt pressured to strive harder than usual.

“I think no nga naay stress of course and pressure na nahitabo sa iyahang life labaw na kay she graduated with flying colors. As first batch sa K-12 pud dako ug expectation ang mga tao like ga look forward sila kung unsa jud ang outcome sa pagbag-o sa curriculum and I think that created pressure within her to strive harder.”

(I think that there is stress of course and pressure that happened in her life especially that she graduated with flying colors. As the first batch of K-12, people have high expectations as they look forward to see what the outcome of the change in the curriculum will be and I think that created pressure within her to strive harder.)

Hardships in Managing Overload of Content

Another challenge that Kawika faced in her journey of passing the LET as first batch product of K-12 curriculum is the management of content. Kawika shared that in her LET preparation, the content and information that K-12 curriculum offered was really overloaded and given the fact that the questions included in the LET was only 150 every area, she did not have any idea what questions will come out.

“The management of the content gyud nga akong na-encounter while naga review or in preparation sa LET kay very broad ang mga contents and information like dako kaayo ug cover nga subject areas and very overloaded ang information sa K-12 curriculum and given the fact nga ang mga questions sa LET is 150 lang every area, wala jud koy ka idea idea unsay manggawas nga questions.”

(The management of the content that I actually encountered while reviewing or in preparation for the LET because the contents and information are very broad like the subject areas are very large and the information is very overloaded in the K-12 curriculum and given the fact that the questions in LET are only 150 in each area, I have no idea what questions will come out.)

To augment Kawika's idea, Rizal confirmed that she saw how Kawika struggled to absorb the topics. This notion leads to the fact that K-12 curriculum offered a wide variety of knowledge in which the participant found hard to adjust with.

“One instance jud nga naka remember ko is nakita nako siya nga nag struggle sa pag absorb sa mga topics.”

(One instance that I remember is when I saw her struggling to absorb the topics.)

Encountering Changes in the Table of Specifications (TOS)

The TOS outlines what topics will be covered in the exam and how much weight each topic carries. With the introduction of the K-12 curriculum, there were shifts in teaching methods and learning goals, which affected the content and distribution of subjects across different grade levels.

This meant that the TOS needed to be adjusted to reflect these changes accurately. According to Kawika, she encountered challenge for there was limited experience and resources available to align the TOS effectively with the new curriculum. The lack of established guidelines made it difficult for her to know precisely what to focus on for the LET. Kawika admitted that she was afraid that time because everything changed including the topics in the exam.

“I think it is because of the thought nga first batch jud mi sa K-12 and madungagan nako sa uban nga lisod jud lagi daw ang LET and for me nga mo-take na sa kadto nga time is among batch jud daw kay ano nausab ang tanan, mausab jud daw ang tanan pati ang mga topics sa exam.”

(I think it is because of the thought that we are the first batch in K-12 and I heard from others that the LET is really difficult, it seems that everything will change, including the topics of the exam.)

Research Question No. 3: What are the ways of coping on the challenges for each case of KCAST LET passers who are first batch products of K-12?

In the third question, the participant was asked how she cope with the challenges she had experienced. Her responses undergo thematic analysis and the researcher identified four emerging themes about coping mechanism. Emerging themes formed are: embracing the changes brought by K-12 curriculum, focusing on one's goals, the benefits of researching topics and asking pieces of advice from other LET passers.

Embracing the Changes brought by K-12 Curriculum

One of the coping strategy that Kawika used was to embrace the changes brought by the K-12 curriculum. She stated that being open to changes helped her to align her study efforts with the new curriculum's objectives and competencies. She saw the need to focus on understanding the updated teaching methods and learning goals emphasized in the K-12 curriculum.

“Lisod jud i-adapt ang changes kay syempre another adjustment nasad but as a competent student sa una, gi embrace nalang sad nako tanan nga gi-introduce sa K-12 curriculum sa akoa like adjusting to my study approaches and knowing unsa nga study habits nga mag work well sa akoa...”

(It is difficult to adapt to the changes because of course there is another adjustment but as a competent student before, I just embraced everything that was introduced in my K-12 curriculum like adjusting to my study approaches and knowing what study habits that will work well for me...)

Meanwhile, Rizal supported the idea of Kawika as she said that she witnessed and observed that Kawika is adaptive to the changes of the K-12 curriculum that benefitted her in the journey of Licensure Examination.

“adaptive siya sa changes and I guess iyang strategy nga gihimo jud is to think nga naay benefits ang K-12 curriculum sa iyaha...”

(she is adaptive to changes and I guess her strategy is to think that the K-12 curriculum has benefits for her...)

Focusing on One's Goals

Focusing on goals is a coping strategy for Kawika, as a first batch of K-12 curriculum when she prepared for the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) because it helped her to have a clear direction and clarity amidst the uncertainties of the transition. By setting clear goals for her LET preparation, she identified what she needs to achieve and she prioritized her efforts accordingly. This strategy allowed her to concentrate on mastering the essential knowledge and skills required for the exam, despite the challenges of adjusting to the new curriculum.

“Focus jud sa akong goal nga makahuman ug skwela kay I believe man gud nga if determined gyud ka nga makalampos and makatabang sa imong family then the length or the years of education will not matter anymore so bisan pag unsa na katas, kung naa kay goal nga makahuman is mohuman jud ka even lisod kaayo siya hunahunaon but you will always be motivated kay naka focus ka sa imong goal.”

(I really focus on my goal of finishing school because I really believe that if you are really determined to succeed and help your family, then the length or the years of education will not matter anymore so no matter how long that years are, if you have a goal you will finish, you will finish even if it is hard to think about it, but you will always be motivated because you are focused on your goal.)

The Benefits of Researching the Topics

As cited by Kawika, researching topics served as a coping strategy for heras preparation for the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) because it helps fill the gaps caused by the newness of the curriculum and the uncertainty surrounding its alignment with the exam.

Since the K-12 curriculum is still relatively new, there might not be enough established materials or resources directly tailored for LET preparation. Kawika stated that by conducting research on various topics likely to appear on the exam, she gathered information from different sources to supplement her understanding of the curriculum and ensure she covered all necessary content areas.

“Akong gibuhad before is researching the topics on my own like after sa klase namo, if I have confusions about the topics, i-research jud na nako para maliwanagan ko and makasabot nako.”

(What I did before is researching the topics on my own like after our class, if I have confusions about the topics, I will research them so that I can understand them.)

In order to support her idea, her close friend Rizal, shared that as what she observed before, whenever Kawika had a hard time understanding topics, she would likely search the internet and then she would easily understand the topics right away.

“pag maglisod na siya kay naga search ra siya sa internet and then makasabot ra man pud siya dayon.”

(when she was having a hard time, she just searched on the internet and then she will understand right away.)

Asking Pieces of Advice from other LET Passers

Since the K-12 curriculum represents a significant shift, learning from those who succeeded under the previous system provided Kawika with valuable guidance on how to approach studying and preparing for the exam effectively. During the interview, she mentioned that during her LET preparation she asked advice from her cousin on how to approach the examination.

“I remember asking advices from my cousin under the old curriculum to siya and mag study lang jud and like the day sa examination gihatagan ko niyag mga tips like dapat sa adlaw jud sa examination, mentally ready jud ko and prepared jud akong lawas.”

(I remember asking advices from my cousin under the old curriculum and she always remind the same thing to me, that I should always study and she gave me tips like in the actual day of the examination, I should be mentally ready and my body should be prepared.)

In addition, Rizal remembered the time when she and Kawika heard advice from their instructors which reminded them to always get rid of negativities and to always focus on the review in order to successfully pass the exam given the fact that they are first batch products of K-12 curriculum.

“nakaagi man jud mig mga teachers nga nakapasar pud sa LET syempre before mi nag take sa exam no kay nagahatag jud na sila ug advice labaw na sa KCAST supportive kaayo ang mga teachers. Ila jud mi pirmi gina remind not to think of negativities, focus lang jud mi pirmi sa review...”

(we also had teachers who passed the LET, of course, before we took the exam, because they are already giving advice, especially in KCAST, the teachers are very supportive. They always remind us not to think of negativities, just focus on the review...)

Research Question No. 4: What are the insights of each case of KCAST LET passers as first batch products of K-12 curriculum?

This question is about the insights of the participant in the challenges, struggle and difficulties she had experience as a KCAST LET passer who is a first batch product of K-12 curriculum. Also, this includes the realization as a LET passer as a pioneer of the K-12 curriculum and advice of the participant to others. In the response of the participant, there are three emerging themes that the researcher has found. The following themes are: giving more emphasis on the practical skills, the Relevance of Aiming for High Outcomes and The Need to Enhance CSA for the Next Batch of LET Takers.

Giving More Emphasis on the Practical Skills

When the researcher asked Kawika on the impact of K-12 transition to her academic journey in the context of LET preparation, she have realized that giving more emphasis on practical skills is crucial because it aligns with the competency-based approach of the curriculum. In addition, she stated that practical skills are essential for teachers to effectively apply their knowledge in real classroom settings. The K-12 curriculum emphasizes hands-on learning and application of concepts, which can better prepare aspiring teachers for the dynamic challenges they may encounter in their teaching careers.

“Those practical skills nga akoang nalearn through hands-on and experiential activities, in terms sa akong career journey mas gi prepare pa ko sa K-12 in experiencing the field of teaching like the evolving educational system and the different approaches and the methods of teaching.”

(Those practical skills that I learned through hands-on and experiential activities, in terms of my career journey, I was more prepared in K-12 in experiencing the field of teaching like the evolving educational system and the different approaches and the methods of teaching.)

The Relevance of Aiming for High Outcomes

Aiming for high outcomes is what the researcher extracted from the response of Kawika when asked about her message to the next batches of KCAST LET takers who are also a product of K-12 curriculum, for Kawika, aiming for high outcome sets a standard of excellence and encourages the next batches to strive for success. As they transition from the K-12 curriculum to preparing for the LET, it's important for students to understand that achieving high scores on the exam can open doors to better career opportunities in teaching. She also emphasized to always never settle for less.

“Aim for the stars never settle for less nga dapat makapasar lang ka. Kailangan mag aim jud ka nga mag top ka kay kung mag aim lang daw ka nga makapasar ka, imong hulugan next is bagsak na ka but if you aim for the top, mahulog paka sa pasar before ka mabagsak, dili man ka ma top so atleast makapasar ka..”

(Aim for the stars never settle for less that you should just pass. You need to aim to be top because if you only aim to pass, you will fall to failure but if you aim for the top, you will pass before you fail, even you will not become a top notcher at least you will pass..)

The Need to Enhance CSA for the Next Batch of LET Takers

Kawika recommended that the institution of KCAST should enhance the Competency Skills Appraisal Area (CSA) or mock board exams for future LET takers. This recommendation stems from her own experience of facing challenges in aligning her preparation with the new K-12 curriculum and the requirements of the LET. She stated that by enhancing the CSA or mock board exams, future

batches can have better preparation materials that closely mirror the content and format of the actual LET. This would help next batches of LET takers become more familiar with the types of questions they will encounter and ensure that their study materials are aligned with the specific topics and competencies assessed in the examination.

“Ako man gud nabantayan before is sometimes nay mismatch nga mahitabo sa topics sa CSA kanang wala kayo siya na in line sa ubang questions nga mga nanggawas and its very needed jud for the next batch because based sa akong experience very lacking jud na siya nga area or sa amoa or sa mga subject areas kadtong mga dating nanggawas sa LET exam like sa review center pa gyud namo nahibal-an ang ubang topics nga much needed unta sa exam.”

(I have also noticed before that there is sometimes a mismatch that happens in CSA topics, sometimes it is not in line with other questions that came out and its very needed for the next batch because based on my experience it is very lacking in that area before or in the subject areas, the questions that previously came out of the LET exam, we just encountered those in the review center, where in fact, those topics are much needed in the exam.

CASE 3- KA-NUMBER

Kanumber, not her real name is also a first batch product of K-12 curriculum who graduated with the degree of Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Mathematics at Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology. She successfully passed the Licensure Examination for Teachers last March 2023.

Kanumber admitted that she had a hard time adjusting with the changes introduced by K-12 curriculum in her journey in passing the LET as the content from her major transitioned into more complex and broad manner.

Research Question No. 1: What are the unique characteristics of each case of KCAST LET passers who are first batch products of K-12 curriculum?

The data gathered regarding the unique characteristics of Kanumber who is a graduate from KCAST and a first batch product of K-12 curriculum from BSED- Mathematics was compressed into three (3) essential themes. These emerging themes are: encountering various forms of Assessment, Expertise in Subject Matter and Pedagogical Knowledge and Critical Thinking Skills.

Encountering Various Forms of Assessment

During the interview, the researcher asked Kanumber on what is her distinct academic background that contributed to her success in passing the Licensure examination for Teachers (LET), she stated that during her K-12 education, she encountered various forms of assessments that developed her familiarity with the answering the questions in the context of the LET.

“I encountered various forms of assessment such as mga quizzes and by engaging with those different types of assessment, I developed such familiarity with the assessment nga murag ma familiar nimo ang questions and how to answer that one.”

(I encountered various forms of assessment such as quizzes and by engaging with those different types of assessment, I developed such familiarity with the assessment that I seem to be familiar with the questions and how to answer that one.)

Expertise on Subject Matter

Kanumber also highlighted that K-12 curriculum provided her with expertise on subject matter. She stated during the interview that she was exposed to various principles and disciplines which became her basis for understanding specific concepts or subject areas that were present during the LET which includes Math, English, Filipino, Science and Social Studies.

“The K-12 specially or the K-12 curriculum especially the mga content gud sa mga subject areas specially apil na dira ang Math, English, Filipino, Science, Social Studies and other subjects pa nga dapat i-take nimo sa LET. Tungod sa K-12, I was exposed to concepts, mga principles and disciplines which kanang nag form siya ug basis for my understanding in that specific or subject areas tested in the Licensure Examination for Teachers.”

(The K-12 especially or the K-12 curriculum especially the contents of the subject areas especially including Math, English, Filipino, Science, Social Studies and other subjects that you should take in the LET. Because of K-12, I was exposed to concepts, principles and disciplines which formed a basis for my understanding in that specific or subject areas tested in the Licensure Examination for Teachers.)

Her informant named Descartes (pseudonym) confirmed her idea by stating that one of the unique characteristics of Kanumber is her expertise when it comes to her majorship and she also added that not all the people are skilled and master in the subject areas but Kanumber was equipped during the Licensure Examination.

“Makaingon ko nga unique na siya it is because naa man siyay kana ganing mastery or expertise sa subjects under her major and not all the people baya is hawd ug mastery sa mga subject areas, but siya kay equipped na jud siya during that time.”

(I can say that she is unique, it is because she has that mastery or expertise in the subjects under her major and not all the people are skilled and master in the subject areas, but she was already equipped during that time.)

Having Pedagogical Knowledge and Critical Thinking Skills

Another unique characteristic of Kanumber is her pedagogical knowledge and critical thinking skills which helped her to be mastered in understanding problems related to her major. She even shared that before, she had a fear of facing Mathematical problems but because of the K-12 education she was able to know how to solve problems.

“Naa ko’y pedagogical knowledge and the critical thinking and hawd na pud ko magsabot ug especially kaning problem solving skills kanang sa una man gud is dili ko into Math jud pero gi face nako akoang, fears, ang Math so tungod sa K-12 na kabalo ko how to solve mga problem.”

(I have pedagogical knowledge and the critical thinking and I am also good at understanding and especially in problem solving skills that at first I was not into Math but I faced my fears in Math so it is because of K-12 I know how to solve problems.)

Her informant supported her idea by stating what she had observed on the participant. She shared that for her, the K-12 curriculum equipped Kanumber with essential skills and knowledge needed for the Licensure Examination for Teachers which involved critical thinking skills and problem-solving abilities.

“Ang K-12 curriculum for me kay syempre nag equip jud sa iyaha with essential skills and knowledge needed for the LET, skills involve critical thinking and problem-solving abilities.”

(The K-12 curriculum for me of course equipped her with essential skills and knowledge needed for the LET, skills involving critical thinking and problem-solving abilities.)

Research Question No. 2: What are the challenges of each case of KCAST LET passers as first batch product of K-12 curriculum?

The data obtained regarding the challenges of Kanumber in her journey in passing the LET as first batch product of K-12 curriculum. The response of the participant was summarized into three (3) essential themes. These include the following: limited peer support, high expectation of people and difficulty to adjust in K-12 transition’s content for LET preparation.

Limited Peer Support

One of the impact of the changes brought by the K-12 curriculum in Kanumber’s journey in the LET was the limited peer support. She shared that during her K-12 education, she had limited access to peers who have experienced the same educational system and LET preparation process. She also added that the lack of peer support and guidance lead her to feelings of isolation and uncertainty on how to navigate the examination process effectively.

“Being the first batch to undergo the K-12 curriculum, we have limited access to peers who have experienced the same educational system and LET preparation process, this lack of peer support and guidance lead us to feelings of isolation and uncertainty about how to navigate the examination process effectively.”

To augment, Descartes acknowledged her idea by confirming that Kanumber really struggled in finding reliable guidance or resources that fitted to her situation due to the fact that she is a product of K-12 curriculum.

“The curriculum’s kana ganing kabag-ohan might have made it harder for her to find reliable guidance or resources nga fitted to her situation.”

(The curriculum’s changes might have made it harder for her to find reliable guidance or resources fitted to her situation.)

High Expectation of People

As said by Kanumber, high expectation of people was one of the challenges that she has experienced as a first batch product of K-12 curriculum. Based on her statement, there are maybe heightened expectations from her parents, teachers and peers as being the pioneer of the K-12 curriculum to perform well in the LET. She was stressed that time because she felt that she was representing the effectiveness of the new curriculum.

“There are maybe heightened expectations from our parents, from our teachers as well as our peers for the first batch of K-12 graduates to perform well in the LET. The pressure to succeed is uhm... made additional stress and anxiety especially if we feel that we are representing the effectiveness of the new curriculum.”

Difficulty to Adjust in K-12 Transition’s Content for LET Preparation

The first batch of products from the K-12 curriculum may lack comprehensive standardized materials and resources specifically tailored for LET preparation. Unlike established curricula with a long history of LET alignment, the initial implementation of the K-12 curriculum may not have had sufficient time to develop and refine materials that directly address the requirements of the licensure examination. Kanumber also had most important experience in regards to this, she stated that she struggled to understand the expectation and requirements of the new curriculum transition which impacted her readiness for the LET exam.

“the transition of K-12 learning system involves adapting to a new curriculum's structure, the content as well as the teaching methodologies. I struggle initially to understand the expectations and requirements of the new curriculum transition with the impact of my readiness for the LET exam.”

Her classmate also affirmed that Kanumber was really challenged to integrate various subjects especially when preparing for a specialized and high-stakes exam like the LET. Additionally, she also struggled to apply her learning from K-12 curriculum to practical settings.

“maybe nag struggle pud siya in integrating various subjects especially when preparing for a specialized and high-stakes exam like the LET. Moreover, ang transition pud from learning nga naa ra sa school or learning and pag abot na sa practical application could have gave difficulties for her.”

(maybe she also struggled in integrating various subjects especially when preparing for a specialized and high-stakes exam like the LET. Moreover, the transition from learning that only inside the school or learning and she struggled to apply it in practical settings.)

Research Question No. 3: What are the ways of coping on the challenges for each case of KCAST LET passers who are first batch products of K-12?

The data obtained regarding the coping mechanism of Kanumber as a KCAST LET passer and a product of K-12 curriculum were summarized into three (4) essential themes. These include the following: focusing on long-term benefits, building collaboration with peers, maintaining positive outlook and asking pieces of advice from other LET passers.

Focusing on Long-term Benefits

Kanumber believes that one of her advantage in approaching the new curriculum is her ability to focus and to always think on the long-term benefits that will come if she will complete her K-12 education journey. She voiced out that K-12 served as her powerful motivator in pursuing high education up to taking the Licensure Examination, she believed that keeping sight of her motivation allowed her to persevere to challenges and setbacks.

“Akong ginahuna huna lang jud is focusing on long-term benefits reminding myself of the long-term benefits and opportunities that come if I complete the K-12 education journey, it can serve me as a powerful motivator whether it's pursuing high education, entering the workforce or pursuing our dreaming career keeping sight of these motivation motivates me to persevere to challenges and setbacks.”

(My only thought is focusing on long-term benefits reminding myself of the long-term benefits and opportunities that come if I complete the K-12 education journey, it can serve me as a powerful motivator whether it's pursuing higher education, entering the workforce or pursuing our dreaming career keeping sight of these motivation motivates me to persevere to challenges and setbacks.)

Her classmate added that Kanumber always reminded herself of the long-term benefits of her education. She testified that Kanumber always thought that everything that she has experienced was for her own good.

“always pud reminded herself of the long-term benefits of her education. Gianhuna huna niya always that para ra sad sa iyahang kaayohan ang tanan.”

(always reminded herself of the long-term benefits of her education. She always thought that everything was for her own good.)

Building Collaboration with Peers

Kanumber believed that collaboration with peers provides opportunities for peer teaching and peer learning, where they can take turns explaining concepts, solving problems, and providing feedback to one another. Teaching others not only reinforces one's own understanding of the material but also fosters critical thinking and communication skills, which are essential for success on the LET. Kanumber stated that forming peer study groups allowed her to collaborate in sharing ideas and build support in understanding and mastering new concepts that are needed in the examination.

“Forming peer study groups allows me to collaborate in sharing ideas and support each other in understanding and mastering new concepts.”

Her classmate from college confirmed Kanumber's idea and she stated that Kanumber was engaging to study groups in which she got ideas from other people who faced the same challenges as her.

“Naga engage pud siya ug mga study groups nga didtoa makakuha siya ug idea sa uban pud nga mga tao nga naga face pud ug parehas nga challenge sa iyaha”

(She also engaged in study groups where she can get ideas from other people who face the same challenges as her.)

Maintaining Positive Outlook

Transitioning from the traditional educational system to the K-12 curriculum may bring about feelings of uncertainty and anxiety due

to the unfamiliarity of the new approach. However, as what Kanumber highlighted, maintaining a positive attitude helped her alleviate these concerns by fostering a mindset of adaptability and resilience. Instead of viewing the changes as obstacles, she perceived them as opportunities for growth and learning.

“I am always maintaining positive outlook, cultivating positive attitude and maintaining confidence is really crucial for success in LET preparation. I am always reminding myself of my past achievements, visualizing success and refraining negative thoughts into positive affirmation can boost my self-confidence and motivation.”

As a matter of fact, Descartes, her classmate from college confirmed her idea as she said that Kanumber likes to set achievable goals for herself and she also loves to celebrate her successes and that positive trait of her helped in maintaining positive outlook.

“Sa pagkaila nako niya kay hilig siya to set goals, set small, achievable goals for herself, celebrated her successes along the way...”

(As I know her, she likes to set goals, set small, achievable goals for herself, celebrated her successes along the way...)

Asking Pieces of Advice to other LET Passers

Kanumber professed that in her journey of preparing for the LET, she listened to the advice of other passers from old curriculum. Kanumber stated that other passers shared their strategies and techniques that were effective for them in preparing for the LET before. She also stated that other LET passers lent their books and advised her to enroll in the review center to ensure that she will pass the exam.

“LET passers from old curriculum shares their strategies and techniques that were effective for them in preparing for the examination especially muana sila nga kanang naa koy mga libro diria, gusto nimo hulamon? Dapat mag adto ka ug review center para matabangan ka or pag mag review center ka best siya or naa juy posibilidad, one hundred percent nga makapasar ka.”

(LET passers from old curriculum share their strategies and techniques that were effective for them in preparing for the examination especially they will offer that I have books here, do you want to borrow them? You should go to a review center to help you or if you go to a review center, there is a possibility, one hundred percent that you will pass.)

Meanwhile, Descartes affirmed to the idea of Kanumber by confirming that she received advice from the LET passers under the old curriculum. Descartes added that old curriculum LET passers emphasized the importance of thorough preparation and reading various resources to successfully pass the exam.

“Nag ask ko sa iyaha and she said nga naka receive siya ug advice from other LET passers under the old curriculum, they emphasized the importance of thorough preparation jud na always nila gina ingon to read various resources, books and always keep your focus...”

(I asked her and she said that she received advice from other LET passers under the old curriculum, they emphasized the importance of thorough preparation because they always say to read various resources, books and always keep your focus...)

Research Question No. 4: What are the insights of each case of KCAST LET passers as first batch products of K-12 curriculum?

The data obtained regarding the insights of Kanumber as KCAST LET passer who is also a product of K-12 curriculum were summarized into three (3) essential themes. These include the following: the need to identify effective study materials, the need to provide active participation on workshops and seminars for LET preparation and the need to enhance CSA for the next batch of LET takers

The Need to Identify Effective Study Materials

The K-12 curriculum introduces new concepts and topics that may not have been covered in traditional education systems. Effective study materials ensure alignment with the curriculum, covering the specific content and skills that will be tested in the LET. Kanumber stated that for the next batches to successfully pass the LET, they should always find review books and online resources which can give insights into which material were most helpful for them in preparing for the LET.

“They must identify effective study materials such as a review books, online resources and LET review courses they can gain insights into which material were most helpful for them in preparing for the LET including those areas or subjects that are aligned well with the K-12 curriculum content and format.”

The Need to Provide Active Participation on Workshops and Seminars for LET Preparation

Seminars and workshops offer opportunities for interactive learning and engagement with experienced educators and LET experts. By actively participating in workshops and seminars, students can gain valuable insights, strategies, and tips on how to effectively approach the LET, especially considering the unique challenges and content of the K-12 curriculum. As a graduate from Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology, Kanumber stated that enhancement of LET preparation programs including seminar and workshops is needed for the institution in order to produce more competent LET passers and even topnotchers.

“In order for them to produce more top notchers and LET passers, my suggestion is to enhance their LET preparation programs by

offering comprehensive review course, workshops and seminars specifically tailor the needs of K-12 graduates. Those programs should cover the content domains, testing format and strategies for success in the LET examination.”

Her classmate, Descartes, explained that Kanumber’s idea was on point as she also believes that providing additional training and support for educators and establishing mentorship programs are crucial in order to aid the needs of the students who are soon to take the LET. Descartes stated creating programs assist the students not only in academic but also in their future career.

“also mag provide ug additional training and support for educators to adapt to the K-12 framework effectively, and establish mentorship programs to assist students in their academic and career pursuits...”

(also provide additional training and support for educators to adapt to the K-12 framework effectively, and establish mentorship programs to assist students in their academic and career pursuits...)

The Need to Enhance the Competency Skills Appraisal (CSA) for the Next Batch of LET Takers

As a product of the first batch K-12 curriculum from Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology, Kanumber shared that what she found lacking in her time was the emphasis and thorough dissemination of topics in the mock board. She recommended that for KCAST to continuously produce competent LET passers, they should provide practice test in order to stimulate the testing environment for the student to have a deep familiarity with the test structure of the licensure examination.

“They have to enhance the mock examination and they should facilitate feedback because if they organize mock LET examination and practice test to stimulate the testing environment and familiarize the student with the format timing types of questions that is found in the LET...”

Her classmate, Descartes added to Kanumber’s idea as she stated that the institution should provide thorough review session in order to practice the students oh how to manage their time during the exam.

“pwede sad nga mas thorough pajud ang CSA especially pwede sad sila mag offer ug review session gud other than the subject nga CSA and also dapat mas i-practice pa pud nila ang students to kana ganing how to manage their time during the exam...”

(They can teach CSA thoroughly especially they can offer a review session other than the subject CSA and also they should practice the students on how to manage their time during the exam...)

CASE 4- KA-CHIKADING

Kachikading, not her real name is a first batch product of K-12 curriculum and a graduate of Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Mathematics program from Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology. She successfully passed the LET last March 2023.

As a product of the newly implemented K-12 system, she faced the challenging task of going through unfamiliar teaching methodologies and adapting to the evolving educational system. Despite her thorough preparation and dedication to her studies, Kachikading found herself struggling with the complexities of the LET, which encompassed a broader range of competencies and skills than old curriculum, which challenged her to demonstrate not only subject matter knowledge but also critical thinking, communication, and pedagogical proficiency.

Research Question No. 1: What are the unique characteristics of each case of KCAST LET passers who are first batch products of K-12 curriculum?

The data gathered regarding the unique characteristics of Kachikading who is a graduate from KCAST and a first batch product of K-12 curriculum from BEED was compressed into three (3) essential themes. These emerging themes are: eagerness and determination to learn, incorporating soft skills and familiarizing important concepts through mnemonics and clues.

Eagerness and Determination to Learn

In the journey of passing the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET), finding eagerness and determination to learn is a unique characteristic of Kachikading. This eagerness and determination stem from her pioneering spirit and the challenges she faced in her journey through a new curriculum. As the first batch of the K-12 curriculum, Kachikading encountered unfamiliar teaching methodologies and a broader scope of skills tested in the LET. However, her eagerness to learn and determination to succeed drive her forward, motivated her to overcome obstacles and adapt to changes easily. This unique characteristic sets her apart, as she embraced the opportunity to grow, develop, and excel. She stated that:

“Kung moingon jud ta nga kanang distinct it talks about for me sa attitude na being determined, able and eager to learn to achieve our dreams. Able to learn how to pass the LET, able to create your own study habits mao na siya ang naka connect pud siya sa amoang course or program.”

(If we say distinct for me it talks about the attitude of being determined, able and eager to learn to achieve our dreams. Able to learn how to pass the LET, able to create your own study habits, and those are connected in our course or program.)

Incorporating Soft Skills

Incorporating soft skills is a unique characteristic of Kachikading, as the first batch of the K-12 curriculum, on her journey of passing the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET). Unlike previous curricula, the K-12 system emphasizes not only academic knowledge but also the development of essential soft skills such as communication, empathy, and adaptability. Kachikading stated that K-12 shaped her to be firm in handling challenges and how to be consistent in that can help in her academic achievement.

“Ang K-12 man gud is does not lang jud siya naga focus sa imong hard skills naga focus pud siya sa imohang soft skills so when we talk about soft skills man dili jud siya more on about sa knowledge. So dira jud sa K-12 is kanang they nurture you also sa imoha ganing behavior how you take the challenges, how you pursue your dreams, how to be consistent in a way nga makahelp sa imohang academic achievement.”

(K-12 does not just focus on your hard skills, it also focuses on your soft skills, so when we talk about soft skills, it does not focus more on knowledge. So here in K-12 is that they nurture you also in your behavior, how you take the challenges, how you pursue your dreams, how to be consistent in a way that can help your academic achievement.)

Her classmate named Piaget (pseudonym) affirmed to her idea by stating that aside from the ability to think logically and rationally, K-12 also developed her affective skills which enabled her to have empathy and humility. She emphasized that soft skills taught Kachikading to handle specific situation that can help in creating peaceful connection with other people.

“nakuha niya sa curriculum is not only her skills to think logically and rationally but also ang iyahang affective gani nga domain, when we say affective domain apil na siya dira ang having empathy and humility like how will you handle specific situation... nga maka help in creating peaceful connection with other people.”

(what she gained in the curriculum is not only her skills to think logically and rationally but also her affective domain, when we say affective domain it includes having empathy and humility like how will you handle specific situation... that can help in creating peaceful connection with other people.)

Familiarizing Important Concepts through Mnemonics and Clues

Familiarizing important concepts through mnemonics and clues is a unique characteristic of Kachikading as the first batch product of the K-12 curriculum in the context of LET preparation. Mnemonics and clues provide students with effective memory aids that facilitate retention and recall of key information. By associating complex concepts with memorable phrases, images, or patterns, Kachikading gained strategy to easily encode, store, and retrieve information during exams and assessments. Kachikading shared that when she went to college she built her own strategy in studying by finding some clues that eventually lead to right answers.

“Niadto mi ug college naanad na mi na kanang more on kana ganing more on memorization nami more on mnemonics nami kanang we really built our own strategy to study tapos when we talk pud also sa mga subject areas and test structures dira na jud nimo siya ma apply nga kanang during mag exam na naa na gani kay mga clues, you will not be able to memorize sa tanan nga mga phrases but kadtong nalang ganing mga clue niya and then the answer.”

(When we went to college, we got used to more on memorization, more on mnemonics, we really built our own strategy to study, then when we talk about subject areas and test structures, you can apply that during the exam there are already clues, you will not be able to memorize all the phrases but those clues and then the answer.)

Research Question No. 2: What are the challenges of each case of KCAST LET passers as first batch product of K-12 curriculum?

The data obtained is about the challenges of Kachikading in her journey in passing the LET as first batch product of K-12 curriculum. The response of the participant was summarized into three (3) essential themes. These include the following: high expectation of people, encountering changes in TOS and difficulty to adjust in K-12 transition's content for LET preparation.

High Expectation of People

High expectations was the significant challenge for the first batch of K-12 curriculum graduates preparing for the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET), especially for Kachikading. As Kachikading was a pioneer of the new curriculum, which introduces changes and updates to the educational system, she felt the importance of her pioneering role that gave her the pressure to perform well and prove the effectiveness of the K-12 program.

“There are a lot of people jud nga ma down tungod sa expectation sa tao because taas man kaayo silag expectation... then at the end of the day baya if dili nimo ma achieve tong ilahang gi expect sa imoha they will judge you, they will judge you as if naa silag contribution sa imohang gihangoan.”

(There are a lot of people who are down because of people's expectations because they have very high expectations... then at the end of the day if you cannot achieve what they expect from you they will judge you, they will judge you as if they have a contribution to your hard work.)

Her classmate, Piaget, acknowledged Kachikading's idea by confirming that she was pressured by other people for she was known as a brilliant student and intelligent student. Given the fact that she was a product of K-12 curriculum, people expected that she knew everything and for her, everything is easy. Piaget also added that people looked up to her to the point that she cannot contain it anymore.

“ang mga challenges nga na encounter niya is really the pressure sa laing tao kay nailhan siya nga brilliant and makita man sad nimo nga intelligent jud siya. Ang mga tawo nag expect na tanan butang para sa iyaha ka sayon ra ...so ingon ana ang na experience ana niya, kanang taas kaayo ug tan-aw ang tao ba to the point nga usahay she can't contain it anymore.”

(the challenges that she encountered are really the pressure of other people because she is known as brilliant and you can also see that she is intelligent. People expect everything for her is easy, so that is what she experienced, people looked up to her to the point that sometimes she cannot contain it anymore.)

Encountering Changes in TOS

The changes in the Table of Specifications became a struggle for Kachikading as the first batch of K-12 curriculum as she was challenged to follow the alignment between the new curriculum and the requirements of the LET, it required her to have careful consideration and adaptation in her preparation journey. She shared that she felt that they became the bait as some of her batch mates did not take the LET immediately for they wanted to spy on the changes made by the PRC on the Table of Specifications.

“Naa man gud toy storya sa una nga kadtong nag take mi ug LET. I do not know if na news ba to siya? Ilang storya is maggawas ug new questionnaire ang PRC, so that time sa amoang batch gamay lang ang nag take ug LET it is because gusto sila maniid. So mahulog ba nga kami tong ilang murag bait, so kami tong bait na ilhang napaon...”

(There is a hearsay before when we took the LET. I do not know if it was in news? They said that the PRC will issue a new questionnaire, so at that time only a few from our batch took LET it is because they wanted to spy. So it seems like we became the bait...)

Meanwhile, Piaget supported Kachikading's idea by sharing that the specific areas or topics that were covered in the licensure examination was not the same as the old curriculum. She stated that:

“As a matter of fact nausab gani ang specific areas or topics nga covered ato nga exam like dili na siya parehas before...”

(As a matter of fact, the specific areas or topics that are covered have changed so the exam is not the same as before...)

Difficulty to Adjust in K-12 Transition's Content for LET Preparation

The difficulty of Kachikading in adjusting K-12 transition contents for LET preparation for the first batch product of the K-12 curriculum caused from the need to reconcile the new educational systems with the established requirements and expectations of teacher licensure examination.

This process requires careful consideration of curriculum alignment, resource development, and instructional strategies to effectively support aspiring teachers in their LET preparation. Kachikading expressed that when K-12 curriculum came, many subjects have changed and during her review, some of the contents were altered to for the new system.

“Pag-abot man gud sa K-12, daghan nausab nga mga subjects, daghag nausab nga mga ways. Pag review gani namo ato, naa toy mga Powerpoint ang mga lecturers naay uban lahi ang nakaflash pero gina correct nila sa amoa ang ilhang mga inputs kay moingon mana sila nga “before man gud wala pay K-12 ingon ani man gyud ang mga information but now, naa nay K-12 e-correct lang ni namo.”

(When K-12 came, many subjects have changed, many ways have changed. When we reviewed before, the lecturers had Powerpoints, some flash are different from what they discussed but they corrected their inputs because they said, "before there was no K-12, the information was exactly the same, but now, that there is K-12 already, we will just correct it.)

Her classmate who also experienced the same situation further stated that during review session, the information presented to her were sometimes outdated. There were books that are no longer allowed to be used and she said that their review masters advised them to be careful with the information for the reason that some things have changed or have been added.

“during review session namo ang mga information from resources sometimes kay outdated na like naay books nga wala na ginapagamit sa amoa or gina ingon nga magbantay daw mi sa information kay maybe naay mga nausab or nadungag.”

(during our review session the information from resources is sometimes outdated like there are books that are no longer used by us or that we should be careful with the information because maybe some things have changed or been added.)

Research Question No. 3: What are the ways of coping on the challenges for each case of KCAST LET passers who are first batch products of K-12?

The data obtained regarding the coping mechanism of Kachikading as first batch product of K-12 curriculum in her journey as KCAST LET passer were summarized into four (4) essential themes. These include the following: maintaining positive outlook, strengthening communication with family, building collaboration with peers and asking Pieces of Advice from Other LET Passers.

Maintaining Positive Outlook

Even when bombarded with challenges and hurdles Kachikading shared that one of the strategies she made to stay motivated is to always look on the bright side of everything. Kachikading instilled in her mind to be positive even when taking the LET was struggling, she shared that LET preparation challenged different aspects of her life physically, financially and even her faith.

The steps that I take that time sa akoang LET is to always take the bright side, always stay positive even though as in kung mga take jud ka ug LET you will be financially challenged, ang imohang physical i-test jud na siya, especially imohang faith.”

(The steps that I take that time in my LET is to always take the bright side, always stay positive even though as in if you take LET you will be financially challenged, your physical will be tested, especially your faith.)

In truancy, Piaget, her classmate agreed with her idea and she confirmed that Kachikading possessed a positive attitude in approaching the changes in curriculum. As for her, she adapted the changes made of the new curriculum by thinking always on the brighter side and she reminded herself during that time of the benefits in which the curriculum could give in her academic endeavor.

“for me she adapted to the changes by K-12 by kanang thinking always on the brighter side of everything like she’s always reminding herself of the benefits of curriculum...”

(for me she adapted to the changes by K-12 by thinking always on the brighter side of everything like she's always reminding herself of the benefits of curriculum...)

Strengthening Communication with Family

For Kachikading, strengthening communication with family while preparing for the licensure exam as the first batch under the K-12 curriculum, is a crucial coping strategy. According to her, family members offer emotional support, encouragement, and understanding during challenging times. By sharing her experience and concern with loved ones, she felt validated, and also received valuable advice on managing stress and balancing responsibilities specifically from her mother. She stated that:

“Akong mama man gud mao jud na pirmo iyang linyada nga okay lang if dili ka makapasas, ang importante ni take ka ug exam. Isa pa, pwede man ka mu take. So ing-ana gani, nga kabalo ka ba nga ang tao ang immediate sa imoha is andam mudawat sa imoha even if you failed...”

(My mom always said that it is okay if you do not pass, the important thing is that you take the exam. You still have another chance to take it again. So with that, you already know that the person who is immediate to you is ready to accept you even if you failed...)

To add on Kachikading’s idea, Piaget, her classmate expressed that Kachikading shared to her that she is really open in communicating with her family which became her strategy to easily cope with the challenges. She added that the support of his family is always with her and she always thinks that her family is also her strength.

“Para to keep motivated she really think of her family kay iyang family man sad gud iyang encourager like sa una gani gina story niya nga open jud daw siya sa iyang pamilya and grabe pud ang support sa iyang family. Sa iyang family siya gakuha jud ug strength.”

(In order to keep motivated, she really thinks of her family because her family is also her encourager like before she said to me that she is open to her family and the support of her family is also great. She gets strength from his family.)

Building Collaboration with Peers

Building collaboration with peers provides opportunities for peer teaching and peer learning, where individuals can take turns explaining concepts, solving problems, and providing feedback to one another. Teaching others not only reinforces one's own understanding of the material but also fosters critical thinking and communication skills, which are essential for success on the LET. Kachikading also coped with stress and challenges by having her study buddy who helped her get rid of fear in failure. She expressed that two is better than one when it comes to sharing of knowledge needed for LET as a first batch product of K-12 curriculum.

“If naa kay study buddy, mawala ang imohang kahadlok nga ma-fail kay syempre muana man ka nga two is better than one so duha nagud mo ana nag study so kung unsa imohang nahibaw-an iyaha man nang i-share sa imoha and vice versa ra pud mo.”

(If you have a study buddy, you will lose your fear of failing because of course you will also know that two is better than one, so both of you can share knowledge and vice versa.)

Her classmate supported her claims that she built relationship with peers as she testified that they used to study before and they are sharing ideas with the concepts that they were confused of.

“Before jud naga uban mi ug study ana niya and mahilig jud mi mag share ug ideas kung naa koy mga butang nga di masabtan mag pangutanan-anay rami...”

(Before we used to study together and we like to share ideas when I have things that I do not understand, we just ask each other...)

Asking Pieces of Advice from Other LET Passers

Amidst the changes made when K-12 curriculum came, Kachikading strived to look for testimonies of other LET passers. For Kachikading, finding a person who have experienced the same thing is the most important source of information. Kachikading shared that there was a particular friend from her church who passed the LET ahead of her and her friend advised to keep in her mindset to study not just for the sake of licensure examination but to study in order to answer the questions correctly.

“Naay particular nga kauban sa church nga nag take sad siya ug LET before... Ana siya ayaw ug study para lang ingon, instead i-mindset nimo nga magstudy ko para naa kay ma-answer sa LET nga tama.”

(There is a particular friend in church who also took LET before ... She said, do not study just for the sake of it, instead you should have the mindset that I will study so that you will be able to answer the LET correctly.)

Her classmate stated that in their college years, they are always reminded by their teacher who have already passed the LET to comprehend the questions that will be included in the examination. In addition, she also added that they are also advised to be prepared always in the examination specially that in their batch, the content and information have been enhanced or changed.

“ginapahinumdom jud mi sa una sa among teachers nga of course nakapasar na to be always prepared jud daw sa day sa exam, mag comprehend sad daw mi ug tarong sa questions and mag study gyud.”

(our teachers remind us before of course those teachers have already passed, they remind us to be always prepared on the day of the exam, we should have comprehension and to study well and answer the questions properly)

Research Question No. 4: What are the insights of each case of KCAST LET passers as first batch products of K-12 curriculum?

The data obtained regarding the insights of Kachikading as KCAST LET passer in her journey as first batch product of K-12 curriculum are summarized into three (3) essential themes. These include the following: the necessity of facilitating in-house review in KCAST, importance of fostering professional development and the need to enhance the CSA for the next batch of LET takers.

The Necessity of Facilitating In-house Review in KCAST

Kachikading expressed her suggestion to the institution of Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology where she graduated to provide in-house review. Kachikading shared that before, in-house review was conducted in KCAST to cater the aspiring LET passers who cannot afford to enroll in review center. As for Kachikading, the institution should bring back the in-house review for it will help the future LET takers to feel encouraged without worrying about financial matters. Through this, the institution may produce more competent LET passers who can bring pride and honor to their alma matter.

“Siguro ang akoa lang pud ma suggest is that, before man gud, naa na silay in-house review, so good pud siya kung ibalik nila no kay there are students man gud nga cannot afford to enroll review center...”

(Maybe the only thing I can suggest is that, before they have an in-house review, so it would be good if they bring that back because there are students who cannot afford to enroll to a review center...)

Piaget, her classmate, confirmed her idea as she said that she heard Kachikading desired for the KCAST to have in-house review. Piaget emphasized the passion of Kachikading to help the students who does not have capability to pay for the review center.

“Madungog nako pirmi sa iyaha nga unta mag offer ang KCAST ug free review para dili luoy ang uban students nga way ikabayad...”

(I always hear her say that KCAST should offer free review so that students can still avail even without money.)

Importance of Fostering Professional Development

One of the significant lessons that Kachikading realized as a first batch product of K-12 curriculum is the importance of fostering professional development. The K-12 curriculum for Kachikading contributed to her professional growth, despite the fact that the new educational system posed difficulties, she can say that the curriculum molded her at an early age to explore the field of education. When she was 17, she already experienced teaching in school for their immersion in Grade 12. Kachikading expressed that K-12 benefitted her by giving a chance to socialize with the higher ranks in education and she was also able to realize and experience how vast and wide is the education in the Philippines especially in her locality.

“For me, it really promotes the professional development because at an early young age, when we were in Grade 12, so ang edad nako ato 17, so when I was 17 I already explored na sa field of education so gipatudlo nami. Then, that really benefitted us kay we are able to socialize with the higher ranks na sa education and then we are able to experience how vast the education in the Philippines especially in our locality.”

(For me, it really promotes the professional development because at an early young age, when we were in Grade 12, so my age was 17, so when I was 17 I already explored the field of education so we already experienced teaching. Then, that really benefitted us because we are able to socialize with the higher ranks in education and then we are able to experience how vast the education in the

Philippines especially in our locality.)

The Need to Enhance the CSA for the Next Batch of LET Takers

When Kachikading was asked by the researcher about her recommendation to the institution of KCAST she expressed that KCAST provided her with value-laden quality education which is really helpful for her in passing the LET. However, there was a certain area that she thought the institution should focus on which is the Competency Skills Appraisal or the CSA. Kachikading said that KCAST should strengthen the CSA and they should facilitate face to face sessions. She added that it is very nice for the next batches of KCAST LET takers to have interactive activities during every session to develop motivation and encourage student's participation which can eventually lead to retention of concepts.

“Strengthen the CSA, i-strengthen jud na nila dira nga review as much as possible nindot gani ug if face to face siya kay kadtong amoa man gud is virtual to siya and then as in struggle kaayo siya if maghinay ang connection, labi na ug kanang bad weather...”

(Strengthen the CSA, they should strengthen the review and as much as possible it is nice if it is face to face because ours before are just virtual and then it seems to be in a lot of struggle if the connection is slow especially if the weather is bad.)

CROSS-CASE ANALYSIS

A case study is a methodological approach that entails a thorough investigation of a certain bounded system while systematically collecting data from various sources. It allows one to look beyond individual case, to the phenomenon; in this case of KCAST LET passers as first batch products of K-12 curriculum, it helps on dealing with the real experiences of KCAST LET passers as first batch product of K-12 curriculum the secrets that only the informants can generate the real life they possessed. The case study method "explores a real-life, contemporary bounded system (a case) or multiple bounded systems (cases) over time, through detailed, in depth data collection involving multiple sources of information and reports a case description and case themes (Gustafsson, 2017).

Moreover, according to Brink (2018) a multiple-case design explores a real-life multiple bounded system through detailed, in-depth data collection involving sources of information. Through using a multiple-case design a wider exploration of the research question and theoretical evolution will enable the researcher to understand the differences. This enables the researcher to address the complex issues that need to be explored in-depth, and to understand the behavioral conditions of such a system, based on comments inputs and interpretative perspectives of the participants. However, the multiple case study design is a valuable qualitative research tool in studying the links between the personal, social, behavioral, psychological, organizational, cultural, and environmental factors that guide managerial and leadership development.

The preceding chapter, in particular chapters 4 to 7, described the experiences and strategies KCAST LET passers used as first batch product of K-12 curriculum in their journey in passing the exam. It also includes the distinctive themes and main points of each participant in each instance. The variations and similarities in the participants' experiences are discussed in this chapter.

Research Question No. 2: What are the challenges of each case of KCAST LET passers as first batch product of K-12 curriculum?

The researcher interviewed the participants and she ended to the three (3) essential themes. These include the following: high expectation of people, difficulty to adjust in K-12 transition's content for LET preparation and encountering changes in TOS.

High Expectation of People

Based on the results of this study, four (4) cases admitted that they experienced high expectation of people that became a challenge for them as a first batch product of K-12 curriculum in the context of preparing for the board exam. Moreover, they expressed that the expectation of people gave them anxiety for they feel pressured by the people around them as they think that they are the ones who will be a testament of the curriculum's effectiveness.

Kalinguist, found it hard to contain the expectation of other people for him as he expressed that during the month of examination he was messaged by his review master who expected that he will top the board. Kalinguist admitted that in the moment he heard that, he did not know what to react or to feel.

“Pag-abot na sa ano, examination namo nga part, month na sa examination namo, nag chat mana amoang kuan gud, review master ana siya na “ready na ba mo mag top?” didto murag wala nako kasabot sa akoang gibati, hala nag expect man diay na sila ug ingon ana ang mahitabo sa akoa diay.”

(During the month of examination our review master messaged me saying “are you ready to top the board” and when I read that I don't know what to feel anymore, they expected that I will top the board.)

Meanwhile, during that period, Kawika opened up about her feelings of fear, which caused from the high expectations placed on her by others and the weight of being a pioneer in the K-12 system. The thought of being the first to experience the new educational system brought about a sense of uncertainty and difficulty. She found herself questioning what it would be like if her peers succeeded while she struggled to keep pace. This internal questioning only served to add the pressure she already felt, intensifying the challenge she

faced. The fear of failure went large in her mind, casting doubts on her ability to meet the expectations placed upon her. Despite her reservations, Kawika knew she had to confront these feelings head-on and find a way to face the obstacles before her.

Table 2. *Themes and Supporting Statements on the Challenges of KCAST LET Passers as First Batch Product of K-12 Curriculum*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
High Expectation of People	<p>“During the month of examination our review master messaged me saying “are you ready to top the board” and when I read that I do not know what to feel anymore, they expected that I will top the board.”- IDI-01</p> <p>“The thought that we are the first batch and then what if I do not pass? Then people have a lot of expectations and what if others will pass and then I will not.” -IDI-03</p> <p>“There are maybe heightened expectations from our parents, from our teachers as well as our peers for the first batch of K-12 graduates to perform well in the LET. The pressure to succeed is uhm... made additional stress and anxiety especially if we feel that we are representing the effectiveness of the new curriculum.”-IDI-05</p> <p>“There are a lot of people who are down because of people's expectations because they have very high expectations... then at the end of the day if you cannot achieve what they expect from you they will judge you, they will judge you as if they have a contribution to your hard work.”- IDI-07</p>
Difficulty to Adjust in K-12 Transition's Content for LET Preparation	<p>“The adjustment to new curriculum especially that K-12 curriculum, the transition of K-12 learning system involves adapting to a new curriculum's structure, the content as well as the teaching methodologies. I struggle initially to understand the expectations and requirements of the new curriculum with the impact of my readiness for the LET exam.” -IDI-05</p> <p>“When K-12 came, many subjects have changed, many ways have changed. When we reviewed before, the lecturers had Powerpoints, some flash are different from what they discussed but they corrected their inputs because they said, "before there was no K-12, the information was exactly the same, but now, that there is K-12 already, we will just correct it.” -IDI-07</p>
Encountering Changes in TOS	<p>“I think it is because of the thought that we are the first batch in K-12 and I heard from others that the LET is really difficult, it seems that everything will change, including the topics of the exam.” -IDI-03</p> <p>“There is a hearsay before when we took the LET. I do not know if it was in news? They said that the PRC will issue a new questionnaire, so at that time only a few from our batch took LET it is because they wanted to spy. So it seems like we became the bait..” -IDI-07</p>

“Ang thought ba nga hala first batch mi unya what if di ko kapasar? Unya daghan na kaayo ug expectation ang mga tao unya ang uban makapasar unya ako dili makapasar” -IDI-03

(The thought that we are the first batch and then what if I do not pass? Then people have a lot of expectations and what if others will pass and then I will not.)

Kanumber, echoing the sentiments of Kalinguist and Kawika, acknowledged the heightened expectations surrounding the graduates of the K-12 system. She shared her belief that people anticipated her to excel in the LET examination, adding to the already considerable pressure to succeed. This additional stress and anxiety weighed heavily on her, impacting her emotional well-being during that period. Kanumber honestly expressed how she felt like her entire batch had become representatives of the effectiveness of the K-12 curriculum. This sense of being under pressure intensified the burden of responsibility she felt, as she struggled with the weight of expectations placed upon her.

“There are maybe heightened expectations from our parents, from our teachers as well as our peers for the first batch of K-12 graduates to perform well in the LET. The pressure to succeed is...made additional stress and anxiety especially if we feel that we are representing the effectiveness of the new curriculum.”- IDI-05

Furthermore, Kachikading admitted that she experienced similar emotions. She revealed that many individuals were feeling discouraged due to the elevated expectations set by others. She expressed her belief that people tend to pass judgment when one falls short of their high expectations. This unfortunate reality saddened her, as she recognized that individuals would criticize without considering the efforts and dedication put into the hard work. The realization that even those who did not contribute to the effort would still judge added to the burden she and others in her situation as first batch product of K-12 curriculum were carrying.

“There are a lot of people jud nga ma down tungod sa expectation sa tao because taas man kaayo silag expectation... then at the end of the day baya if dili nimo ma achieve tong ilahang gi expect sa imoha they will judge you, they will judge you as if naa silay contribution sa imohang gihagoan.”- IDI-07

(There are a lot of people who are down because of people's expectations because they have very high expectations... then at the end of the day if you cannot achieve what they expect from you they will judge you, they will judge you as if they have a contribution to your hard work.)

Difficulty to Adjust in K-12 Transition's Content for LET Preparation

Being able to easily adapt to the K-12's new content for LET preparation is crucial for the first batch product of the curriculum.

However, Kanumber struggled to adjust with the new curriculum especially that it involves adapting to new teaching methodologies and new structure of content. Kanumber admitted that she struggled initially to understand the requirements of the new curriculum that impact her readiness for the Licensure Examination for Teachers.

“The adjustment to new curriculum especially that K-12 curriculum, the transition of K-12 learning system involves adapting to a new curriculum's structure, the content as well as the teaching methodologies. I struggle initially to understand the expectations and requirements of the new curriculum with the impact of my readiness for the LET exam.”- IDI-05

Furthermore, Kachikading expanded on her point by highlighting the significant changes brought about by the implementation of K-12. With the introduction of K-12, numerous subjects underwent modifications, leading to changes in various aspects of the educational system. During review sessions, Kachikading observed differences in the teaching materials, such as PowerPoint presentations and flashcards, compared to what was previously used. However, the lecturers made adjustments to ensure alignment with the new K-12 curriculum. They acknowledged that while the information remained largely the same before K-12, the implementation of the new curriculum necessitated updates and corrections to ensure relevance and accuracy in line with the evolving educational system. She uttered:

“during review session namo ang mga information from resources sometimes kay outdated na like naay books nga wala na ginapagamit sa amoa or gina ingon nga magbantay daw mi sa information kay maybe naay mga nausab or nadungag.”- IDI-07

(when K-12 came, many subjects have changed, many ways have changed. When we reviewed before, the lecturers had Powerpoints, some flash are different from what they discussed but they corrected their inputs because they said, "before there was no K-12, the information was exactly the same, but now, that there is K-12 already, we will just correct it.)

Encountering Changes in TOS

As one of the first to experience the new educational system, it was anticipated that numerous changes would accompany the journey. However, Kawika encountered significant challenges with the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) due to the extent of the changes. Kawika believed that the difficulty caused from the reason that they were the pioneer batch under the K-12 system. Additionally, Kawika heard from others that the LET exam had become more challenging. This added to the difficulty, as it appeared that everything, including the exam topics, had undergone significant changes. She stated:

“I think it is because of the thought nga first batch jud mi sa K-12 and madungagan nako sa uban nga lisod jud lagi daw ang LET and for me nga mo-take na sa kadto nga time is among batch jud daw kay ano nausab ang tanan, mausab jud daw ang tanan pati ang mga topics sa exam.” -IDI-03

(I think it is because of the thought that we are the first batch in K-12 and I heard from others that the LET is really difficult, it seems that everything will change, including the topics of the exam.)

Kachikading agreed with Kawika and shared that there were rumors circulating before they took the LET exam. Some people mentioned hearing it on the news. They said that the Professional Regulation Commission (PRC) would use a new questionnaire. Due to this, only a few from their batch decided to take the LET exam, thinking they were being watched. Kachikading even mentioned that it felt like they were being used as bait.

“Naa man gud toy storya sa una nga kadtong nag take mi ug LET. I don't know if na news ba to siya? Ilahang storya is maggawas ug new questionnaire ang PRC, so that time sa amoang batch gamay lang ang nag take ug LET it is because gusto sila maniid. So mahulog ba nga kami tong ilang murag bait, so kami tong bait na ilahang napaon...”-IDI-07

(There is a hearsay before when we took the LET. I do not know if it was in news? They said that the PRC will issue a new questionnaire, so at that time only a few from our batch took LET it is because they wanted to spy. So it seems like we became the bait..)

Research Question No. 3: What are the ways of coping on the challenges for each case of KCAST LET passers who are first batch products of K-12?

In the data the researcher has gathered, she concluded into five (5) emerging themes. These include the following: embracing changes brought by the K-12 curriculum, building collaboration with peers, strengthening communication with family, maintaining positive outlook and asking pieces of advice from other LET Passers.

Embracing Changes Brought by the K-12 Curriculum

Despite the hurdles, two individuals believed that embracing the new curriculum could be beneficial. Kalinguist expressed the belief that being introduced to the new curriculum was intertwined to stepping into the unknown future. He emphasized the importance of embracing the new curriculum, especially given the introduction of K-12. Since the future is uncertain, he shared that it was essential to adapt to changes in philosophies, visions, and missions of schools. Kalinguist believed that by embracing the new curriculum, individuals could align themselves with the evolving educational landscape and be better prepared for whatever the future holds. He shared:

Table 3. *Themes and Supporting Statements on the Coping Mechanisms of KCAST LET Passers as First Batch Product of K-12 Curriculum*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Themes</i>
Embracing Changes Brought by the K-12 Curriculum	<p>“What all of us did is we have to embrace the new curriculum especially that we are being introduced with the K-12 itself we do not know what future offers us so therefore, if ever the philosophies, vision and mission of our school changes, all of the things will follow so we have to embrace this” -IDI-01</p> <p>“It is difficult to adapt to the changes because of course there is another adjustment but as a competent student before, I just embraced everything that was introduced in my K-12 curriculum like adjusting to my study approaches and knowing what study habits that will work well for me..” -IDI-03</p>
Building Collaboration With Peers	<p>“Within the school, inside the classroom, what we foster is love, support and understanding. So that made me or that became a strategy for me that I should also bring in college like I have to understand that all of the people are different, I have to understand that we have come on terms that we have different ideas but we should stick on something that is beneficial for us.” -IDI-01</p> <p>“Forming peer study groups allows me to collaborate in sharing ideas and support each other in understanding and mastering new concepts.” -IDI-05</p> <p>“If you have a study buddy, you will lose your fear of failing because of course you will also know that two is better than one, so both of can share knowledge and vice versa.”-IDI-07</p>
Strengthening Communication with Family	<p>“Talk with my family especially if I cannot contain it anymore, I have a lot of things in mind especially that I am close to being professional, my last step to get a license, you have to talk with someone especially your loved ones. Talk with them or say what your problems.” -IDI-01</p> <p>“My mom always said that it is okay if you don't pass, the important thing is that you take the exam. You still have another chance to take it again. So with that, you already know that the person who is immediate to you is ready to accept you even if you failed” -IDI-07</p>
Maintaining Positive Outlook	<p>“I am always maintaining positive outlook, cultivating positive attitude and maintaining confidence is really crucial for success in LET preparation. I'm always reminding myself of my past achievements, visualizing success and refraining negative thoughts into positive affirmation can boost my self-confidence and motivation.” -IDI-05</p> <p>“The steps that I take that time in my LET is to always take the bright side, always stay positive even though as in if you take LET you will be financially challenged, your physical will be tested, especially your faith.” -IDI-07</p>
Asking Pieces of Advice from other LET Passers	<p>“For me I get advices from the top notchers before who are English Majors, even if I do not know them personally, I messaged them on Facebook, ask their opinions on how they study? What are their study habits? What they can say for us who are new batch.” -IDI-01</p> <p>“I remember asking advices from my cousin under the old curriculum and she always remind the same thing to me, that I should always study and she gave me tips like in the actual day of the examination, I should be mentally ready and my body should be prepared.” -IDI-03</p> <p>“LET passers from old curriculum share their strategies and techniques that were effective for them in preparing for the examination especially they will offer that I have books here, do you want to borrow them? You should go to a review center to help you or if you go to a review center, there is a possibility, one hundred percent that you will pass” -IDI-05</p> <p>“There is a particular friend in church who also took LET before ... She said, don't study just for the sake of it, instead you should have the mindset that I will study so that you will be able to answer the LET correctly.” -IDI-07</p>

“What all of us did is we have to embrace the new curriculum especially that we are being introduced with the K-12 itself we do not know what future offers us so therefore, kung unsa man na ang philosophies, vision and mission sa atoang school if that changes all of the things will follow so we have to embrace this.”-IDI-01

(What all of us did is we have to embrace the new curriculum especially that we are being introduced with the K-12 itself we do not know what future offers us so therefore, if ever the philosophies, vision and mission of our school changes, all of the things will follow so we have to embrace this)

Kawika also affirmed Kalinguist's idea, acknowledging the difficulty of adapting to the changes brought about by the new curriculum. Despite the challenges, Kawika emphasized her competence as a student and her ability to adapt to new circumstances. She shared that she embraced everything introduced in her K-12 curriculum, including adjusting her study approaches and identifying study habits that suited her well. Despite the initial adjustments required, her willingness to embrace change and her positive approach to learning enabled her to adapt the new curriculum successfully.

“Lisod jud i-adapt ang changes kay syempre another adjustment nasad but as a competent student sa una, gi embrace nalang sad nako tanan nga giintroduce sa K-12 curriculum sa akoo like adjusting to my study approaches and knowing unsa nga study habits nga mag work well sa akoo..” -IDI-03

(It is difficult to adapt to the changes because of course there is another adjustment but as a competent student before, I just embraced everything that was introduced in my K-12 curriculum like adjusting to my study approaches and knowing what study habits that will work well for me..)

Building Collaboration with Peers

Building collaboration with peers is essential despite the challenges because it fosters a supportive and inclusive learning environment where individuals can share knowledge, resources, and experiences. Kalinguist confirmed the significance of this during his K-12 education, emphasizing the importance of love, support, and understanding within the school and classroom environment. He noted that this approach became a strategy for him to carry into college, recognizing the diversity of people and ideas. Kalinguist highlighted the need to come to terms with these differences and to focus on pursuing common goals that benefit everyone. This perspective revealed the value of collaboration in fostering understanding, respect, and unity among peers, ultimately contributing to a positive and enriching learning experience for all involved.

“Within the school, inside the classroom, what we foster is love, support and understanding. So that made me or that became a strategy for me that I should also bring in college like I have to understand that all of the people are different, I have to understand that we have come on terms that we have different ideas but we should stick on something that is beneficial for us.”-IDI-01

Furthermore, Kanumber affirmed Kalinguist’s idea, highlighting that she employed the same strategy to stay motivated during her journey in passing the LET as a pioneer of the K-12 curriculum. She emphasized the importance of forming peer study groups, which enabled her to collaborate with others in sharing ideas and supporting each other in understanding and mastering new concepts. This approach not only facilitated academic learning but also fostered a sense of camaraderie and mutual support among peers. By using the knowledge and resources of the group, Kanumber found motivation and encouragement to overcome challenges and achieve success in her academic pursuits especially in her preparation for the Licensure Examination for Teachers.

“Forming peer study groups allows me to collaborate in sharing ideas and support each other in understanding and mastering new concepts.”-IDI-05

Kachikading also agreed with Kalinguist’s and Kanumber’s idea and she added that having a study buddy can be really helpful. Kachikading emphasized the importance of building collaboration with peers as she shared that having connection with someone who shares the same goal as you can lessen the fear of failing as she said that two is better than one.

“If naa kay study buddy, mawala ang imohang kahadlok nga ma-fail kay syempre muana man ka nga two is better than one so duha nagud mo ana nag study so kung unsa imohang nahibaw-an iyaha man nang i-share sa imoha and vice versa ra pud mo.” –IDI-07

(If you have a study buddy, you will lose your fear of failing because of course you will also know that two is better than one, so both of can share knowledge and vice versa.)

Strengthening Communication with Family

Communication with family is extremely important as it creates an atmosphere that allows family to express their differences as well as problems in life. Kalinguist shared that during his LET preparation as a pioneer of K-12 curriculum, he faced obstacles that made his journey challenging. Kalinguist uttered that during those hard times he experienced, he talked to his family and say what his problems are. If he has a lot of things in mind or he cannot understand what he is feeling, he always finds time to communicate his thoughts in order to lessen the burden that he felt during that time. He uttered:

“Talk with my family especially if I cannot contain it anymore, I have a lot of things in mind especially that I am close to being professional, my last step to get a license, you have to talk with someone especially your loved ones. Talk with them or say what your problems.” –IDI-01

Moreover, Kachikading added to Kalinguist’s idea by stating that knowing that you have your family that is ready to accept you even you fail is significant. She shared that in her journey in taking the LET she face doubts as she is a pioneer of the K-12 but her mother reminded her not to worry for she will be accepted whatever the results will be.

“Akong mama man gud mao jud na pirme iyang linyada nga okay lang if dili ka makapasar, ang importante ni take ka ug exam. Isa pa, pwede man ka mu take. So ing-ana gani, nga kabalo ka ba nga ang tao ang immediate sa imoha is andam mudawat sa imoha even if you failed...”-IDI-07

(My mom always said that it is okay if you do not pass, the important thing is that you take the exam. You still have another chance to take it again. So with that, you already know that the person who is immediate to you is ready to accept you even if you failed...)

Maintaining Positive Outlook

A positive outlook empowers pioneers of the K-12 curriculum, especially in their journey towards the LET, by fostering open-mindedness, flexibility, and receptiveness to new ideas and approaches. Kanumber emphasized the importance of maintaining a positive attitude, cultivating confidence, and nurturing self-belief for success in LET preparation. She shared her strategy of constantly reminding herself of past achievements, visualizing success, and transforming negative thoughts into positive affirmations. By doing so, Kanumber enhances her self-confidence and motivation, enabling her to approach challenges with resilience and determination. This positive mindset not only strengthens her ability to adapt to new learning methodologies and content but also fosters a proactive approach to overcoming obstacles and achieving success in her LET journey. She uttered:

“I am always maintaining positive outlook, cultivating positive attitude and maintaining confidence is really crucial for success in LET preparation. I am always reminding myself of my past achievements, visualizing success and refraining negative thoughts into positive affirmation can boost my self-confidence and motivation.” –IDI-05

In addition, Kachikading agreed to the idea of Kanumber and she emphasized the importance of always looking on the bright side and maintaining a positive attitude, even in the face of challenges. She acknowledged that taking the LET exam can bring about financial challenges, physical exhaustion, and even test one's faith. However, Kachikading highlighted the significance of staying optimistic and focusing on the positive aspects of the journey. By adopting a positive mindset, individuals can overcome obstacles with resilience and determination, ultimately paving the way for success in the LET exam. This optimistic outlook not only helps to alleviate stress and anxiety but also fosters a sense of hope and confidence in one's abilities to overcome adversity and achieve their goals.

“The steps that I take that time sa akoang LET is to always take the bright side, always stay positive even though as in kung mga take jud ka ug LET you will be financially challenged, ang imohang physical i-test jud na siya, especially imohang faith.” –IDI-07

(The steps that I take that time in my LET is to always take the bright side, always stay positive even though as in if you take LET you will be financially challenged, your physical will be tested, especially your faith.)

Asking Pieces of Advice from other LET Passers

Connecting with other LET passers indeed creates a sense of community and support among pioneers, fostering a collaborative learning environment where individuals can share experiences, offer encouragement, and provide motivation for one another. Kalinguist shared his experience, expressing that he sought advice from top-notchers who were English Majors. Despite not knowing them personally, he reached out to them through Facebook, asking for their insights on studying strategies, study habits, and any advice they could offer to newcomers like himself. This proactive approach allowed Kalinguist to learn from the experiences and expertise of others, gaining valuable perspectives and guidance that contributed to his own preparation for the LET.

“For me kay ang akoang ginakuhaan ug advice is kadtong mga topnotcher gud nga mga English majors sa una although wala ko kaila sa ilaha. I messaged them on Facebook, ask their opinions on unsaon nila pag study unsa ilahang mga study habits, unsa ilahang makaingon sa amoa, sa mga newbatch”-IDI-01

(For me I get advice from the top notchers before who are English Majors, even if I do not know them personally, I messaged them on Facebook, ask their opinions on how they study? What are their study habits? What they can say for us who are new batch.)

Furthermore, Kawika supported this idea by sharing her own experience. She recalled seeking advice from her cousin, who had undergone the old curriculum. Her cousin consistently emphasized the importance of consistent studying. Additionally, her cousin provided practical tips, such as being mentally prepared on the actual day of the examination and ensuring her body was physically ready. This advice not only highlighted the significance of diligent preparation but also underscored the importance of mental and physical readiness for the challenges ahead. Kawika's cousin's guidance served as a valuable reminder of the essential steps needed to succeed in the LET, reinforcing the importance of seeking advice from experienced individuals.

“I remember asking advices from my cousin under the old curriculum to siya and mag study lang jud and like the day sa examination gihatagan ko niyag mga tips like dapat sa adlaw jud sa examination, mentally ready jud ko and prepared jud akong lawas.”-IDI-03

(I remember asking advices from my cousin under the old curriculum and she always remind the same thing to me, that I should always study and she gave me tips like in the actual day of the examination, I should be mentally ready and my body should be prepared.)

In addition, Kanumber also shared her experience, noting that LET passers from the old curriculum generously shared their strategies and techniques that proved effective for them in preparing for the examination. She mentioned that some even offered their study materials, such as books, as a helpful resource. Furthermore, Kanumber highlighted the suggestion from some LET passers to consider enrolling in a review center for additional support. According to them, attending a review center significantly increased the likelihood of passing the exam. Their willingness to share resources and offer advice demonstrated a sense of camaraderie and support among LET passers, giving view to the importance of collective knowledge and resources to enhance preparation for the LET.

“LET passers from old curriculum shares their strategies and techniques that were effective for them in preparing for the examination especially muana sila nga kanang naa koy mga libro diria, gusto nimo hulamon? Dapat mag adto ka ug review center para matabangan ka or pag mag review center ka best siya or naa juy posibilidad, one hundred percent nga makapasar ka.”-IDI-05

(LET passers from old curriculum share their strategies and techniques that were effective for them in preparing for the examination especially they will offer that I have books here, do you want to borrow them? You should go to a review center to help you or if you go to a review center, there is a possibility, one hundred percent that you will pass.)

Finally, Kachikading emphasized the advice she received from a particular friend at church who had taken the LET before. Her friend emphasized the importance of studying with purpose, rather than simply going through the motions. Instead of studying for the sake of it, Kachikading's friend encouraged her to adopt the mindset of studying to understand and apply the material effectively, ensuring that she would be able to answer the LET questions correctly. This advice emphasized the significance of studying with intention and focus,

highlighting the importance of grasping the concepts and skills necessary to succeed on the examination. By internalizing this mindset, Kachikading and others could approach their LET preparation with determination and purpose, increasing their chances of success.

“Naay particular nga kauban sa church nga nag take sad siya ug LET before ... Ana siya ayaw ug study para lang ingon, instead i-mindset nimo nga magstudy ko para naa kay ma-answer sa LET nga tama.” –IDI-07

(There is a particular friend in church who also took LET before ... She said, do not study just for the sake of it, instead you should have the mindset that I will study so that you will be able to answer the LET correctly.)

Research Question No. 4: What are the insights of each case of KCAST LET passers as first batch products of K-12 curriculum?

After the discussion with the participants, the researcher gathered three (3) essential themes. These include the following: the need to provide active participation on Workshops and Seminars for LET Preparation; Importance of Fostering Professional Development and The Need to Enhance CSA for the Next Batch of LET Takers.

Table 4. Themes and Supporting Statements on the Insights of KCAST LET Passers as First Batch Product of K-12 Curriculum

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
The Need to Provide Active Participation on Workshops and Seminars for LET Preparation	<p>“In terms of teaching training programs before we are sent to schools to have the OJT, we have seminars, workshops, we should do something, we should be active participants of that seminar but the problem we have that time is it was done through online but I hope now that they should do the trainings and workshops physically because in that way they can train the student-teacher well in handling their contents, physical abilities and they can also work well in the exam.” -IDI-01</p> <p>“In order for them to produce more top notchers and LET passers, my suggestion is to enhance their LET preparation programs by offering comprehensive review course, workshops and seminars specifically tailor the needs of K-12 graduates. Those programs should cover the content domains, testing format and strategies for success in the LET examination.” -IDI-05</p>
Importance of Fostering Professional Development	<p>“Hopefully they can strengthen more the professional development to the students now sa mga students karon especially to the 4th year and 3rd year students especially that the 3rd year has the Teaching Profession subject. Hopefully that your teacher would be critical and they would be more knowledgeable about giving you the code of ethics and the philosophy of education...” -IDI-01</p> <p>“For me, it really promotes the professional development because at an early young age, when we were in Grade 12, so my age was 17, so when I was 17 I already explored the field of education so we already experienced teaching. Then, that really benefited us because we are able to socialize with the higher ranks in education and then we are able to experience how vast the education in the Philippines especially in our locality.” -IDI-07</p>
The Need to Enhance CSA for the Next Batch of LET Takers	<p>“I have also noticed before that there is sometimes a mismatch that happens in CSA topics, sometimes it is not in line with other questions that came out and its very needed for the next batch because based on my experience it is very lacking in that area before or in the subject areas, the questions that previously came out of the LET exam, we just encountered those in the review center, where in fact, those topics are much needed in the exam.” -IDI-03</p> <p>“They have to enhance the mock examination and they should facilitate feedback because if they organize mock LET examination and practice test to stimulate the testing environment and familiarize the student with the format timing types of questions that is found in the LET” -IDI-05</p> <p>“Strengthen the CSA, they should strengthen the review and as much as possible it is nice if it is face to face because those ours before are just virtual and then it seems to be in a lot of struggle if the connection is slow especially if the weather is bad.” –IDI-07</p>

The Need to Provide Active Participation on Workshops and Seminars for LET Preparation

Two out of four cases suggested that there is a need to provide active participation on workshops and seminars for LET preparation in the next batches of KCAST LET takers who are also under the K-12 curriculum. Workshops and seminars offer opportunities for interactive learning experiences where participants can engage with expert instructors, ask questions, and receive immediate feedback. This active participation facilitates deeper understanding of the subject matter and enhances retention of key concepts and strategies relevant to the LET.

Kalinguist suggested that teaching training programs, particularly those before undergoing On-the-Job Training (OJT) in schools, should include seminars and workshops where participants actively engage and participate. However, he highlighted a challenge faced during his time, where these activities were conducted online. He expressed hope that such trainings and workshops would now be conducted physically, as he believes this would better prepare student-teachers in handling their content, physical abilities, and exam preparation. Kalinguist emphasized the importance of hands-on training and face-to-face interaction as these methods allow for a more comprehensive learning experience, enabling student-teachers to develop practical skills and confidence in their abilities.

“In terms of teaching training programs before mi gipa OJT sa mga schools, we have seminars workshops, dapat we should do something, we should be active participants of that seminar kaso ang problem lang namo that time is online lang siya, but I hope ang mga trainings or naay workshops nga term karon ang mga seminars they should do it physically kay in that way mas ma train ang mga

student- teachers sa pag handle sa ilahang contents, sa ilahang physical abilities and also mas makatrabaho silag maayo sa exam.” – IDI-01

(In terms of teaching training programs before we are sent to schools to have the OJT, we have seminars, workshops, we should do something, we should be active participants of that seminar but the problem we have that time is it was done through online but I hope now that they should do the trainings and workshops physically because in that way they can train the student-teacher well in handling their contents, physical abilities and they can also work well in the exam.)

Meanwhile, Kanumber expanded on Kalinguist’s idea by suggesting enhancements to LET preparation programs. She proposed offering comprehensive review courses, workshops, and seminars specifically tailored to the needs of K-12 graduates. Kanumber emphasized that these programs should cover the content domains, testing format, and strategies for success in the LET examination. By customizing the training to address the unique challenges and requirements of K-12 graduates, Kanumber believes that educational institutions can better equip aspiring teachers with the knowledge, skills, and confidence needed to excel in the LET and become top-notchers. This approach aims to enhance the effectiveness of LET preparation programs, ultimately contributing to the overall quality of educators entering the teaching profession. She uttered:

“In order for them to produce more top-notchers and LET passers, my suggestion is to enhance their LET preparation programs by offering comprehensive review course, workshops and seminars specifically tailor the needs of K-12 graduates. Those programs should cover the content domains, testing format and strategies for success in the LET examination.” –IDI-05

Importance of Fostering Professional Development

Fostering professional development in K-12 curriculum graduates who will take the LET is crucial for preparing them to become effective and competent educators. Kalinguist emphasized the importance of strengthening professional development initiatives, particularly for current students, especially those in their fourth and third years of study. He highlighted the significance of the Teaching Profession subject, which aims to instill critical thinking skills and enhance knowledge about the code of ethics and philosophy of education among aspiring teachers. By equipping students with these foundational principles and essential competencies, educators can better navigate the complexities of the teaching profession, uphold professional standards, and provide quality education to their future students. Additionally, fostering professional development ensures that educators remain updated with the latest pedagogical approaches, teaching strategies, and educational trends, allowing them to continuously enhance their teaching practices and adapt to the evolving needs of learners and the education system. Overall, investing in professional development programs for K-12 curriculum graduates preparing for the LET is essential for nurturing a cadre of well-prepared and dedicated educators who can positively impact the lives of students and contribute to the advancement of the teaching profession.

“Hopefully mas ma strengthen pa nila ang professional development sa mga students karon especially mga 4th years and 3rd year students kay naa may Teaching Profession karon nga subject ang mga 3rd year hopefully ang teacher ana ninyo is that they would be kanang critical, they would be more kanang knowledgeable about giving you the code of ethics and the philosophy of education...” - IDI-01

(Hopefully they can strengthen more the professional development to the students now sa mga students karon especially to the 4th year and 3rd year students especially that the 3rd year has the Teaching Profession subject. Hopefully that your teacher would be critical and they would be more knowledgeable about giving you the code of ethics and the philosophy of education...)

However, Kachikading has a different perspective. She believed that promoting professional development begins at an early age, as exemplified by her own experience. Kachikading shared that during her Grade 12 year, at the age of 17, she already had the opportunity to explore the field of education and engage in teaching activities.

This early exposure allowed her to socialize with individuals in higher ranks of education and gain firsthand experience of the breadth of education in the Philippines, particularly in her local community. Kachikading emphasized that this early immersion in the field not only enriched her understanding of education but also fostered her professional growth and development. By providing students with opportunities for hands-on experience and interaction with professionals in the field, Kachikading believes that the K-12 curriculum can effectively promote the professional development of future educators, equipping them with the skills, knowledge, and confidence needed to excel in their teaching careers.

“For me, it really promotes the professional development because at an early young age, when we were in Grade 12, so ang edad nako ato 17, so when I was 17 I already explored na sa field of education so gipatudlo nami. Then, that really benefitted us kay we are able to socialize with the higher ranks na sa education and then we are able to experience how vast the education in the Philippines especially in our locality.”-IDI-07

(For me, it really promotes the professional development because at an early young age, when we were in Grade 12, so my age was 17, so when I was 17 I already explored the field of education so we already experienced teaching. Then, that really benefitted us because we are able to socialize with the higher ranks in education and then we are able to experience how vast the education in the Philippines especially in our locality.)

The Need to Enhance CSA for the Next Batch of LET Takers

Enhancing CSA can indeed help bridge the gap between theory and practice by providing practical experiences and opportunities for pre-service teachers to apply their learning in real-world settings. However, Kawika highlighted a crucial issue regarding the alignment of CSA topics with the LET exam content. She noted that there is sometimes a mismatch between the topics covered in CSA and the questions that actually appear on the LET exam. Kawika emphasized the importance of addressing this discrepancy, as it can lead to gaps in knowledge and preparation among aspiring teachers. Based on her experience, Kawika observed that certain topics covered in review centers were actually more relevant to the LET exam than those covered in CSA. Therefore, she emphasized the need for CSA to focus on incorporating content that directly aligns with the exam requirements, ensuring that pre-service teachers are adequately prepared for the challenges they will face in the LET. By addressing this issue, CSA can better fulfill its role in preparing future educators for success in the teaching profession.

“Ako man gud nabantayan before is sometimes may mismatch nga mahitabo sa topics sa CSA kanang wala kayo siya na in line sa ubang questions nga mga nanggawas and its very needed jud for the next batch because based sa akong experience very lacking jud na siya nga area or sa amoa or sa mga subject areas kadtong mga dating nanggawas sa LET exam like sa review center pa gyud namo nahibal-an ang ubang topics nga much needed unta sa exam.”-IDI-03

(I have also noticed before that there is sometimes a mismatch that happens in CSA topics, sometimes it is not in line with other questions that came out and its very needed for the next batch because based on my experience it is very lacking in that area before or in the subject areas, the questions that previously came out of the LET exam, we just encountered those in the review center, where in fact, those topics are much needed in the exam.)

Additionally, Kanumber emphasized the need for the institution of KCAST to enhance the mock examination process and provide feedback to students. She suggested that organizing mock LET examinations and practice tests would help simulate the testing environment and familiarize students with the format, timing, and types of questions found in the LET. By conducting these mock exams, students can gain valuable experience and confidence, allowing them to identify areas for improvement and refine their test-taking strategies. Furthermore, Kanumber emphasized the importance of providing feedback to students based on their performance in these mock exams. Constructive feedback can help students understand their strengths and weaknesses, allowing them to focus their efforts on areas that need improvement and ultimately enhancing their preparedness for the LET. Overall, enhancing the mock examination process and providing feedback are essential components of LET preparation, and implementing these measures can significantly contribute to the success of students taking the LET.

“They have to enhance the mock examination and they should facilitate feedback because if they organize mock LET examination and practice test to stimulate the testing environment and familiarize the student with the format timing types of questions that is found in the LET” –IDI-05

Finally, Kachikading echoed the sentiments of Kawika and Kanumber, emphasizing the need to strengthen the Competency Skills Appraisal (CSA) and the review process. She suggested that CSA should be reinforced, and the review sessions should be enhanced to provide more effective preparation for the LET. Kachikading expressed a preference for face-to-face interactions during these sessions, noting that virtual meetings, as experienced in the past, could pose challenges, particularly if the internet connection is slow or if the weather conditions are unfavorable. By conducting review sessions in person, Kachikading believes that students can benefit from more immersive and interactive learning experiences, facilitating better engagement and understanding of the material.

“Strengthen the CSA, istoryngthen jud na nila dira nga review as much as possible nindot gani ug if face to face siya kay kadtong amoa man gud is virtual to siya and then as in struggle kaayo siya if maghinay ang connection, labi na ug kanang bad weather...” –IDI-07

(Strengthen the CSA, they should strengthen the review and as much as possible it's nice if it is face to face because those ours before are just virtual and then it seems to be in a lot of struggle if the connection is slow especially if the weather is bad.)

Conclusions

One of the significant challenges encountered by graduates of the K-12 curriculum pertains to the continual changes in content and teaching methods, which subsequently impact the level of difficulty in the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET). The evolving nature of the curriculum necessitates interventions aimed at ensuring that upcoming batches of graduates are equipped with comparable experiences, techniques, and mechanisms to effectively navigate the examination landscape and mitigate associated challenges. To address this, an effective approach is essential, involving the enhancement of teacher training programs to align with the evolving curriculum, the development of tailored review courses and workshops targeting updated content and methods, collaborative efforts between educational institutions and professional organizations to provide comprehensive support, and ongoing research to inform interventions and strategies for LET preparation. By implementing proactive measures, educators can better prepare graduates for success in the licensure examination and the teaching profession amidst the evolving landscape of K-12 education.

The findings of the study enable researchers to look into the real-life experiences of KCAST LET passers who are first batch products of K-12 curriculum. With this data in hand, it is clear that these LET passers encountered a number of challenges as a pioneer of the

curriculum. These challenges included high expectation of people, difficulty to adjust to K-12 transition's content for LET preparation and encountering changes in TOS.

Even when faced with challenges KCAST LET Passers who are also pioneers of K-12 curriculum were able to succeed. KCAST LET passers used techniques such as embracing changes brought by K-12 curriculum, building collaboration with peers, maintaining positive outlook, strengthening communication with family and asking pieces of advice to other LET passers.

The study implies to Department of Education (DepEd) and Commission on Higher Education (CHED) officials to provide various workshops as well as to align the new curriculum to the professional undertaking of students. The K-12 curriculum should be further enhanced in order to lessen the burden of students in preparation not only for the LET but also to other board exams. This study allows the higher bodies of education to prioritize the alignment of its content in shaping students who are well-equipped in their future endeavors be it in high-stakes examination.

To the institution of Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology, the LET passers are the testament of the continued pursuit of the institution in producing competent individuals in the society. On the other hand, the study emphasizes the areas they should develop in order to continue its legacy. The school administrators can provide adequate support in conducting workshops and seminars that aims to prepare individuals for the LET. Furthermore, facilitating review sessions that aims to strengthen the knowledge and skills of students for the LET is also needed.

Finally, the future researcher may use the study as a reference for their future research undertakings. Given the fact that the study revealed the hardships and struggles of KCAST LET passers as first batch products of K-12 curriculum, may this undertaking motivate them to have future research endeavors that can be directed to investigate LET passers in their journey as products of the new educational system through qualitative design.

Without a doubt, this research study was effective in achieving its main objective regarding the experiences of KCAST LET passers as first batch products of K-12 curriculum with their distinctions, lived experiences, ways of coping with challenges, and insights towards the next batches of LET takers with the same situation. It is demonstrated by the fact that key themes derived from this journey were able to provide sufficient information and explanation of the same experience. Thus, it is recommended that the school strengthen the implementation of mock board and provide seminars and workshops for next batch of LET takers.

for the students having difficulty learning mathematics.

Regardless, it should be noted that this research paper is not the culmination of all research devoted to investigating the aforementioned topic inquiry. This means that the researchers humbly acknowledged the fact that the findings of this study are just descriptions and cannot be considered generalizations. This is because the researchers only asked for the thoughts and insights of the KCAST LET passers as first batch products of K-12 curriculum. Therefore, the researchers suppose that there are still uncharted avenues and opportunities for future studies.

It is suggested that a larger research study be conducted with a larger number of participants and should include a wider range of educational settings to obtain more substantive answers to the questions presented in this study, as well as performing a further interview with some participants to see if perspectives and insights on the events have not altered over time and can be used in the study. Furthermore, it suggested that more research be done on the KCAST LET passers who are products of K-12 curriculum, assuming that there are still undiscovered dimensions and breakthrough events for further future studies.

Finally, aspiring researchers are encouraged to use similar approaches and strategies, or perhaps try new approaches, to validate or disprove the findings of this research study. Future researchers may replicate or re-conduct the study at different research sites in order to triangulate and provide reliable and reputable research results or outcomes.

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